

University of the Philippines
OPEN UNIVERSITY

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

MASTER OF ARTS IN NURSING

RHODORA MAE SOLIS

**COMMUNICATION COMPETENCY AND EMPATHY AMONG NURSES IN THE
INTENSIVE CARE UNIT OF TERTIARY HOSPITALS IN SAUDI ARABIA**

Thesis Adviser:

ASST. PROF. QUEENIE R. RIDULME
Faculty of Management and Development Studies

30 August 2023

Permission is given for the following people to have access this thesis/dissertation, subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy and any contractual obligations:

Invention (I)	Yes or No ✓
Publication (P)	✓ Yes or No
Confidential (C)	Yes or No ✓
Free (F)	Yes or No ✓

Student's signature:

Thesis adviser signature:

University Permission Page

COMMUNICATION COMPETENCY AND EMPATHY AMONG NURSES IN THE INTENSIVE CARE UNIT OF TERTIARY HOSPITALS IN SAUDI ARABIA

“I hereby grant the University of the Philippines a non-exclusive, worldwide, royalty-free license to reproduce, publish and publicly distribute copies of this Academic Work in whatever form subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy and any contractual obligations, as well as more specific permission marking on the Title Page.”

“I specifically allow the University to:

Specifically, I grant the following rights to the University:

- d. Upload a copy of the work in the theses database of the college/school/institute/department and in any other databases available on the public internet*
- e. Publish the work in the college/school/institute/department journal, both in print and electronic or digital format and online; and*
- f. Give open access to the work, thus allowing “fair use” of the work in accordance with the provision of the Intellectual Property Code of the Philippines (Republic Act No. 8293), especially for teaching, scholarly and research purposes.*

Rhodora Mae Solis (Date)

Signature over Student Name and Date

Acceptance Page:

This Special Project titled: “**COMMUNICATION COMPETENCY AND EMPATHY AMONG NURSES IN THE INTENSIVE CARE UNIT OF TERTIARY HOSPITALS IN SAUDI ARABIA**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Course.

QUEENIE R. RIDULME
Adviser

29 January 2024
(Date)

ASST. PROF. RITA C. RAMOS
Critic

29/01/2024
(Date)

MS. MA. ELMA L. MIRANDILLA
Panel Member

30 January 2024
(Date)

MS. GRACE RIEGO DE DIOS
Panel Member

31 January 2024
(Date)

RIA VALERIE D. CABANES
Panel Member & Program Chair

06 February 2024
(Date)

JOANE V. SERRANO
Dean

Faculty of Management and Development Studies

07 February 2024
(Date)

Biographical Sketch

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to extend my deepest gratitude to the following people who were instrumental in the making of this thesis.

To Assistant Professor Queenie R. Ridulme my research adviser, for the shared expertise and scrutiny of the research paper;

To the research panelists, Assistant Profesor Rita C. Ramos, Chairman of the thesis defense, Assistant Professor Ria Valerie D. Cabanes, Ms. Ma. Elma L. Mirandilla and Ms. Grace Riego de Dios, members respectively; for the professional and intellectual support in the improvement of the thesis;

To Mr. Khalid Abdulla Almslam, thank you for the encouragement you have shared to the research and for inspiring to finish my thesis;

To Mr. Mark Francis Solis, RN, MAN, for the advices and kind assistance in the improvement of the thesis;

Most importantly, 'To my parents Mama Amada and Papa Frank, in loving memory'.

To my sister Sharon with Lendie, Sharlen and Chesca, Sheryl with Jetlord, Peah, Sheng and Butch, Irma with Ian, Liam and Frankliam, my brother Intoy with Mitch, Frachel and Isang, Ariel with Janiel, and my youngest brother Mark Francis, who offered constant prayer intentions to make the study in accordance with the standard set and none of this would have been possible without the their love and patience. I would like to express my heart-felt gratitude to them.

Above all, to, the Source of Life, All - Goodness and Knowledge, Our Almighty GOD, for his loving presence and continuous blessings, guidance and wisdom, which made the reseach paper a reality.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page	i
University Permission Page	ii
Acceptance Page	iii
Biographical Sketch	iv
Acknowledgment	v
Dedication	vi
Table of Contents	vii
List of Tables	ix
List of Figures	x
ABSTRACT	xi
CHAPTER I: THE RESEARCH PROBLEM	1
Background of the Study	1
Statement of the Problem	4
Objectives of the Study	4
Significance of the Study	5
Scope and Limitation of the Study	6
CHAPTER II: THEORETICAL BACKGROUND	8
Review of Related Literature	8
<i>Communication Competency</i>	8
<i>Challenges of Communication Competency</i>	11
<i>Strategies to Improve Communication Competency</i>	12
<i>Empathy Defined</i>	13
<i>Relationship of Communication Competence & Empathy</i>	17
<i>Challenges to Empathy</i>	18
<i>Demographic Profile & Communication Competence</i>	21
<i>Demographic Profile & Empathy</i>	22
<i>Culture & Communication Competence</i>	24
Theoretical Framework	25
Conceptual Framework	27
Operational Definition of Terms	28
Hypothesis	29
CHAPTER III: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	30
Communication Competency and Empathy Among Nurses...	xi

Research Design	30
Sampling Design	30
Research Instrument	31
Data Gathering Procedure	35
Ethical Considerations	38
CHAPTER IV: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	40
Results and Discussion	40
CHAPTER V: SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS	54
Summary of Findings	54
Conclusions	55
Recommendations	56
REFERENCES	58
APPENDICES	68
Appendix A: Questionnaire/Tool for Data Collection	69
Appendix B: IRB Approval	72
Appendix C: Approval to use Toronto Empathy Questionnaire	73
Appendix D: Gantt Chart	74
Appendix E: Approval to use SPCC	76

List of Tables

Table 1 Demographic Profile	40
Table 2 Self- Perceived Communication competence among nurses in the ICU	42
Table 3 Level of Empathy among Nurses in the ICU	44
Table 4 Significant Relationship between the Level of Self Perceived Communication Competence and Level of Empathy of the Respondents	48
Table 5 Significant Relationship between the Communication Competency & Profile of nurses in the ICU	50
Table 6 Significant Relationship between the Empathy and Profile of nurses in the ICU in terms of demographic profile	52

List of Figures

Figure 1 Schematic Diagram	27
Figure 2 Data Gathering Procedure	37

ABSTRACT

Intensive Care Unit (ICU) is a highly stressful and unique environment. Caring for a diverse client population requires nurses effective communication and empathy. These traits, in turn, help to improve patient care and outcomes, increase the level of patient satisfaction, and decrease adverse events. These also promote effective decision making, problem-solving, and encourage good collaboration with fellow health workers. The purpose of the present study is to determine the relationship between Communication Competence and Empathy among Nurses in the Intensive Care Unit of Tertiary Hospital in Saudi Arabia. The respondents consisted of 243 ICU nurses, and the tools used were a Self -Perceived Communication Competence Scale and Toronto Empathy Questionnaire. Descriptive correlational statistics were used to analyze the data. Results revealed that the Self-Perceived Communication Competence among nurses in the ICU is High in contexts such as in public and in group with strangers, friends and acquaintances; and the nurses have high level of empathy. It was also revealed in the results that level of communication competence and level of empathy have no significant relationship. However, the level of communication competence is significantly linked to educational attainment of nurses; while the level of empathy is significantly correlated to age , nationality and length of experience of the nurses.

Chapter I

THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

Background of the Study

With increasing cultural diversity among nurses, grows the concerns relating to the miscommunication. Language limitations made it more difficult to provide care and increased stress and workload (Gerchow et al., 2021). Effective communication and empathy are critical skills for nurses working in the intensive care unit. Murillo et al. (2017) state that personality factors associated with communication skills in ICU nurses are below compared to nurses in another unit. Adequate hand-off information is essential to cultivating positive perceptions of patient safety (Lee et al., 2016).

The majority of nurses hired by Saudi Arabia's Ministry of Health Hospitals come from the Philippines and India. These medical practitioners frequently have little understanding of Islam and Saudi culture. According to Al Sulaimani (2014), in order to improve their abilities in providing care for patients from a variety of cultural backgrounds, they must have formal education and training in the Arabic language as well as Saudi Arabia's cultural customs and values.

Critical choices, very stressful circumstances, and moral conundrums are commonplace in the intensive care unit. Even with this terrible reality, some people still prefer to work in this setting (Scholtz, 2016). Caring for the patients in the Intensive Care Unit requires effective communication and in-depth knowledge of nursing practice, cardiovascular physiology, technology, and pharmacology. It also needs knowledge of direct patient care for ventilator patients, reduction of nosocomial infection, prevention of pressure ulcers, relieving work stress and prevention of COVID-19.

Critical care nurses had vital role in preventing and battling the magnitude in the health, social, emotional, and mental effects from the coronavirus pandemic. We all became witnesses of the pandemic surge in the year 2020. Faced with the threat of this pandemic, deep reserves of compassion, resiliency, kindness, hard work, skilled profession, empathy, and determination prevails. In this aspect, the mechanism of planning and collaborating with multidisciplinary team to have safe immediate movement of patients, expanding of Intensive Care Unit setting to accommodate patients affected with COVID-19, preparation of equipment such as personal protective equipment, imposed thermal scanning to hospital entry points, universal masking social distancing, city lockdown and proper usage of gears decrease the spread of the COVID-19 influenced patient safety outcomes.

The training of healthcare workers in collaboration with Nursing education and Infection Control team to manage the increasing numbers of critically ill patients and cross infection when handling ventilated and non-ventilated COVID patients. Risk assessment, safety inspection and emergency preparedness, dedicated COVID-19 rapid response team, proper linen usage and scrub suit management, housekeeper safety, proper usage of PAPR and cleaning of assistive devices necessary to keep patient and family and healthcare professionals safe.

Communicating to patients' family regarding visitation restriction and interactive communication using social media applications to the patient's family and relatives is of great importance to provide emotional support. The online educational courses, information thru LED television in allocated spots of the hospital provided educational support that meets a change in service delivery process in healthcare setting.

In each communication situation, communication competency aids in delivering messages that are suitable and impactful. Communication between a nurse and

patient is often hindered by the patient's cognitive alterations and devices such as mechanical ventilation (Issennagger et al., 2018). Communication that is necessary always complies with the norms and expectations of the circumstance. When there is effective communication, both parties involved may accomplish their objectives.

Social competency is a soft talent that facilitates more effective patient communication. It supports the patient's motivation and the development and maintenance of a therapeutic connection. It ensures high standards of treatment quality as well as a high degree of attention satisfaction among patients and their families. It has a good effect on nurses and keeps them from burning out. Research indicates that nurses often possess low to medium levels of social competence (Rodak et al., 2019).

According to Almutairi (2015), there is a communication gap that arises between patients and healthcare professionals that exhibit inadequate cultural competency. The government offers programs for foreign healthcare professionals, but more has to be done to enhance education and orientation materials about Saudi Arabian language and culture.

Adams (2017) describes that most ICU nurses consider communicating with families a vital part of their role and then describes supportive behaviors. However, they perceive significant barriers to effective communication. Few of the barriers arise because of effective decisions on their part, and some are beyond control. These barriers often result in nurses believing that families have received sub-optimal information and support. According to Duarte et al. (2016), compassion weariness and compassion satisfaction are positively correlated with empathic worry.

Conversely, the interprofessional connections inside the intensive care unit are

intricate, and nurses encounter a range of pressures such as emotional, communication, and collaboration-related problems. Knowledge about communication competence among nurses is a crucial area for quality improvement in the ICU.

This study determined how communication competence relates to empathy among nurses in the Intensive Care Unit where the quality of care and patient safety are of utmost importance.

Statement of the Problem

Communication can make people interact with each other to provide quality care and promoting patient safety. Nurses' poor communication skills can influence the occurrences of medical errors in ICU nursing performance (Son et al., 2013). Factors including age, gender, culture, educational attainment, current work position, nationality and length of ICU experience needs to be studied in how it can affect the communication competencies and empathy of an ICU nurse.

Research Objectives

The purpose of this study was to ascertain how nurses in the intensive care unit of a tertiary hospital in Saudi Arabia related to communication skills and empathy.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of communication competence among nurses in the ICU in terms of:
 - 1.1 public;
 - 1.2 meeting;
 - 1.3 group;
 - 1.4 dyad;

- 1.5 stranger;
 - 1.6 acquaintance;
 - 1.7 friendship.
2. What is the level of empathy among nurses in the ICU?
 3. Is there a significant relationship between the communication competence and empathy among nurses in the ICU of a tertiary hospital in Saudi Arabia?
 4. Is there a significant relationship between the communication competence and profile of nurses in the ICU in terms of?
 - 4.1 age;
 - 4.2 gender;
 - 4.3 educational attainment.
 - 4.4 current work position;
 - 4.5. nationality;
 - 4.6 length of ICU experience.
 5. Is there a significant relationship between the empathy and profile of nurses in the ICU in terms of?
 - 5.1 age;
 - 5.2 gender;
 - 5.3 educational attainment;
 - 5.4 current work position;
 - 5.5. nationality;
 - 5.6 length of ICU experience.

Significance of the Study

The result of the study would provide the necessary resources and insights and would considerably benefit the following:

Staff Nurses. The results will give the nurses with a deeper insight on communication and use of empathy as well as its importance when performing their duties and responsibilities in the hospital.

Nursing Department. Leadership in nursing may benefit from an awareness of such factors to create effective strategies in communication and using empathy. Provide additional knowledge to support the nursing practice environment.

Patients. Being the recipients of care, the knowledge and the effects of this study will promote quality of care since it has been a fact that the communication competency and empathy among nurses affect the quality of attention to the patients.

Hospital. It will create an image of the institution on what nurses have in terms of their ability to communicate and provide empathy. Consequently, the hospital may offer training and other forms of orientation on how to foster and strengthen communication and empathy among their nurses.

The Researcher. This study empowered the researcher with knowledge in using effective communication and empathy. The learning will also promote management insights for future actions and recommendations.

Future Researchers. The results of this study may serve as a source of knowledge and reference for future researchers who would like to expand the reviews on the Effect of Communication Competency and Empathy among the Nurses in the Intensive Care Unit of Tertiary Hospital in Saudi Arabia.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study was about Communication Competence and Empathy among Nurses in the Intensive Care Unit of Tertiary Hospital in Saudi Arabia. Communication

competence only focused on the competence of the nurses in communicating during the situations of which one might need to communicate such as communicating to public, group, dyad, meeting, friends, stranger, and acquaintances. On the other hand, empathy is focused on the awareness of the feeling and emotions of other people, which can be developed as a skill by any ICU nurses to be applied to their patients.

The study was conducted at Tertiary Hospital, Saudi Arabia. There were 243 respondents who are both male and female ICU nurses presently working in the ICU of Tertiary Hospital in Saudi Arabia. The respondents only included those who have been in service for more than one year because these respondents have already adjusted to their environment, especially adapting the culture and the language.

Chapter II

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

This chapter reviews significant literature and studies that will enrich the appreciation and conduct of this study. It is through several kinds of literature and studies included that it connotes a strong indication that there existed a strong basis of the survey that will be conducted.

Review of Related Literature

Communication Competency

Communication competency is the ability to effectively exchange information to patients, families, and multidisciplinary team. It is a nursing habit that exemplifies what nurses appreciate in their line of work (Piazza, 2015). A psychological quality known as clinical communication competency enables communicators to effectively satisfy their needs and functionally accomplish desired outcomes through clinical communication activities (Merckaert et al., 2015).

Good communication skills can help nurses become more environment-adaptable, increase nursing quality, strengthen their bonds with patients, and lower the incidence of medical conflicts (Curtis et al., 2013).

Developing human resources in nursing is essential for the performance of the organization (Lee et al., 2015). Nursing administrators should work to raise nurses' emotional intelligence and sense of self-efficacy in order to help them communicate more clinically (Zhu et al., 2016). Additionally, it is critical to create a patient-centered communication competence improvement program that enhances the professionalism and emotional intelligence of intensive care unit (ICU) nurses while promoting the development of an innovative organizational culture (Park & Oh, 2018).

The greatest person to assess one's own communication skills with recipients and in a given scenario is the individual. Evaluate self-perceived competence in four situations (dyadic, meeting group, public), with regard to three targets (stranger, acquaintance, and friend), and using self-report assessment when the goal is to learn about the subjects' perceptions, the reasons, and the results of these perceptions.

Effective public speaking and interpersonal communication depend heavily on nonverbal cues including mood, manner, posture, eye contact, voice tone, and fluency (Kristanto & Kurniawati, 2020). Participating in a normal public speaking class reduces anxiety which proves that public speaking training has a substantial effect on anxiety (Neelam, 2018).

Meeting described as a linear process in which information is sent from a source to a recipient (Wheelan, 2003). The communication stream and the society of the observed meetings mixed in terms of the physical setting, frequency, time, and duration. The subjects for the workplace meetings were primarily useful with aim on clinical processes. A well-organized team and a good structural environment not only enhance employee condition but also the patients' health and safety. Overall, the meetings were regarded not only as a chance to convey information top-down but also a means by which personnel could impact decision-making and progression at the work.

Groups are characterized as more than three but less than 20 people having a dialogue. According to the article by (Hong and Bae, 2019), the communication competency of respondents turned out to be significantly higher in the following: a group in which ego-resilience is higher, a group in which feeling is higher, and a group in which self-leadership is higher. The results of the study indicate that efforts in increasing ego-resilience, feeling and self-leadership are required to improve the

communication competency among healthcare workers. Although group communication can take many different forms, having a leader or facilitator guide the discourse will provide the greatest outcomes, particularly in larger groups. Although it's not required, it does greatly reduce chaos. If everyone in the group feels respected and included in the discourse, then everyone will gain from it and contribute more (Skills & Activities for Effective Group Communication, 2017).

Dyad is when two people have a face-to-face conversation with one another. It may be strangers or close friends that actively engaged in the communication process. People interact with one other in person and work out their concerns. The dynamics within the dyad, as well as the individuals' personalities and communication styles, influence the dyad's communication. Members of dyads who have been together for a long time, for instance, could speak more casually than members of dyads who are just starting to know one another (Peep Strategy, 2022).

Every coworker is initially a stranger, and establishing social ties with new colleagues at work is what helps people feel comfortable and at home. However, research has shown that conversing with strangers may frequently have unexpected benefits for people, despite the fact that some people appear reluctant to do so (Oztekin et al., 2020). Fear that other people won't like them or be interested in chatting to them is another reason why people can shy away from approaching strangers (Epley & Schroeder, 2014).

The degree of acquaintance between communicators, the number of people in attendance, the formality of the situation, and other factors can all potentially influence someone's willingness to communicate when interacting with a friend or acquaintance.

Numerous studies have demonstrated that those with strong bonds—such as

partners or close friends—feel as though they understand one another (Riordan & Trichtinger, 2017). They are able to use their unique shared knowledge to pick the most effective course of action, which allows them to communicate more precisely and effectively than strangers (Pollmann & Krahmer, 2018).

Challenges of communication competency

In the critical care unit, communicating in uncertainty with patients and their families is difficult and requires effort and expertise. It affects the nurses working environment to provide quality care to critically ill patients (Drews, 2013). Secure and dependable patient care has been demonstrated to be characterized by the presence of effective communication among healthcare team members (Weller et al., 2014). It serves as the basis of trust and mutual understanding. It is essential in developing a rapport with patients. It has a say in nursing roles such as patient assessment, education, and counseling. It has been shown that a given communication problem does not resolve by time or clinical experience. It can either facilitate the development of a therapeutic relationship or create barriers.

Difficulty in communicating can lead to negative emotions and acute confusion. It is found that ICU professionals experience problems in 50% of interactions with mechanically ventilated patients (Issennagger et al., 2018). The inability of ventilated patients to communicate reported to be a source of distress and causes frustration for nurses. When patients are unable to express their symptoms, degrees of discomfort, and requirements verbally, nurses become frustrated (Kourkouta & Papathanasiou, 2014).

Five intensive care units in Britain were used to study nurse-patient communication. The results indicated a favorable correlation between nurses'

communication and patients' capacity for feedback and communication. Ineffective communication negatively affects patient care and outcomes. These can be a low level of patient satisfaction and higher mortality (Song et al., 2017).

According to the article by Yoo, Lim and Shim (2020), It was more difficult for ICU nurses to communicate with patients, their families, and caregivers than it was to carry out basic nursing tasks (such as giving medications, suctioning, and using various mechanical devices). Their communication problems were either systemic or nurse-to-patient and family-related. Different issues in an ICU are associated with different levels of urgency; patients who are hemodynamically unstable, have respiratory failure, or are experiencing a cardiac arrest, for instance, could be given precedence.

Strategies to improve communication competency

1. Staff training - It is essential to have staff training to provide effective communication through learning modules, printed cards, guideline documents, and structured notes.

2. Innovations - Several novelties have been tested since the COVID-19 epidemic began. The primary areas of improvement are care delivery and communication.

3. Time visits - As a means of communication, virtual visits have been made available due to hospital visitation limitations. It is necessary to organize schedules to see family members.

4. Resources limitation: These include not providing every patient and family member with appropriate access to the social worker. Suggest determining who is most likely to need assistance with referrals.

5. Process: There are opportunities to improve communication in two situations:

(a) Transfer from ICU: Collaborating with family members upon moving patients out of ICU is significant. The guarantee from the healthcare team to family that there is follow-up by the rapid assessment in critical events team.

(b) End-of-life care/palliative care: To make sure that the family feels supported throughout the process and that discussions about care objectives are realized, these conversations require excellent communication.

6. Structure: This includes the following: (a) Culture: There might be some reservations to acknowledge uncertainty openly, and a culture of uncertainty is inevitable is encouraged to help facilitate those types of discussions.

7. Acknowledgment and trust: By include family members in decision-making and designating a family representative and a single ICU team contact to minimize misunderstanding and prevent false information from being spread, trust may be developed toward a shared objective (Alhussaini, 2021).

Empathy Defined

The foundation of delivering comprehensive, personalized, and courteous service in an empowering manner is empathy (Sinclair et al., 2017). It is a human trait, a professional state, and a communication process, in caring for unique relationships (Zeighami, 2012). It is an essential tool to employ during the interaction between nurses and patients (Usta et al., 2012). Empathy understands others feeling and their meaning and convey these emotions to others.

It is a multifaceted concept with components related to cognition, affect, behavior, and ethics. Perception and communication abilities, particularly active listening, are its primary foundations. The altruistic motive is reflected in the ethical component (Ouzouni, 2012).

The cognitive aspect includes analytical and intellectual perceptions of an individual's view. Emotion in oneself can appreciate circumstances, approaches, reasons, and perspectives in life. It promotes interest about strangers, encounter prejudice and determine team spirit, listen, and develop an impressive imagination.

The capacity to empathize with others' inner and emotional states is known as the affective dimension. Emotion comprehension in others has the capability to comprehend the patient's condition, views, and moods; transfer that understanding and patterned its correctness and then act on that kindness with the patient. It enables to understand, connect, and perform for active and high-quality therapeutic relationship with the patient understanding. Health care professionals frequently employ empathy, a human quality, to empower and engage their patients. It is thought to provide the sufferer a positive, appreciated, and cherished feeling (Ficarra, 2018). It is a crucial facet of total clinical competency that has a strong correlation with successful patient outcomes (Kataoka et al. 2018).

The behavioral aspect reflects on the empathetic relationship. The frequency of actions that engage higher-order empathic responses and show adequate sensitivity, such as pro-social helping behaviors when the participant reports feeling compelled to assist someone in need.

In terms of sympathetic physiological arousal, permanent night shift nurses exhibit more sympathetic activity during sleep than regular morning shift nurses, according to 2009 research by Chung et al. Over time, working night shifts may have an impact on nurses' sleep patterns. based on the research done by Ono et. sympathetic nerve tone rose in both circumstances, according to al (2012).

Demonstrating empathy for the unpleasant emotions of another individual results

in elevated physiological activity and perceived stress. The way in which various subjective aspects are understood influences the physiological reactions to empathy. While knowing negative emotions decreased bilateral frontal processes, communicating negative feelings was thought to engage the right temporal area of the brain.

Due to differences in language, culture, and religion, as well as obstacles in patient-provider communication and workplace rudeness, foreign-born nurses encounter a number of difficulties at work (Alosaimi & Ahmad, 2016). The majority of foreign nurses expressed dissatisfaction with their work-life balance (Alreshidi, & Alsharari, 2021). As nurses loaded by different human relationships with healthcare professionals, patients, and caregivers during clinical practice and this in turn causes stress, which has a negative effect on successfully forming significant relationships (Han, 2010).

According to Levett-Jones et al. (2019), a systematic review that examined the efficacy of empathy training for undergraduate nursing students found evidence that training in empathy and communication skills enhances nursing students' capacity for empathy and that nursing communication education plays a predictive role in students' capacity for empathy (Ozturk & Kacan, 2022).

Although developing empathetic abilities is a difficult process, rich life experiences can help. These compassionate abilities support the delivery of quality nursing care. These are transferable abilities that are necessary for partnerships based on collaboration. To be active members of the nursing profession, nurses must possess certain abilities.

Communicating with empathy

Nurses' empathy toward ICU patients is essential to ensure patients adhere to treatment. The majority of nurses exhibit emotional empathy during end-of-life care,

which is followed by pity and cognitive empathy. When interacting with families in end-of-life circumstances, nurses must demonstrate and exercise both emotive and cognitive empathy (Guerrero, 2019). It is beneficial to develop emotional competence, which may help nurses in handling emotional interactions with patients and in promoting well-being at work.

Also, the nurses will require empathy so that they can meet informational needs to reassure patients and their families about health and condition. It also enables nurses to understand patient experiences so that they can identify the needs and resolve concerns.

It is important to have consideration to word choice when providing explanations on patient health status. Paying close attention to the way communications are conveyed might help families make better decisions during trying times. The interdisciplinary team should be conscious of how much time is spent sharing facts with family's vs giving them opportunity to voice their hopes and concerns. In having family meetings, there is a noticeable decrease in stress symptoms and an increase in family satisfaction, according to Rhoads and Amass 2019. Without empathy in the ICU department, it is difficult for family members to provide the needed care for their ill patients (Del Santo et al., 2014).

Nurses with an empathetic approach can better understand the reactions of their patients to health problems, as well as the purpose and source of these reactions. More efforts should be made to build strategies for nurses to enhance their empathic and communication skills so that they can provide adequate care (Kahriman, 2016). Consumers who experienced more compassionate service would later demonstrate greater empathy for other people (Chen & Xu, 2021).

In some instances, people are excited or happy when others are excited or happy. In a state of excitement people think and behave very differently (Patel et al., 2017) which can also be contagious to others. According to the study of Shensheng (2019), there is a multifaceted nature of concerns for social justice, self-evaluation, and social identity.

According to the study of Light et al (2019) While in the company of someone who is experiencing bad emotions, one might show good emotions in order to help the other feel less negative by encouraging the other person to feel positive emotions (for example, by trying to "cheer" the person). Similar to this, someone might express happiness to make someone else happy even if they are only feeling neutral or pleased already. We might refer to this kind of positive-valence empathy as empathetic cheerfulness. Moreover, a person may feel pleasure vicariously in reaction to another person's happy feeling. (e.g., enjoy making other people better) which referred to empathic happiness.

Relationship of communication competence and empathy

Redmond (1985) discovered a strong correlation between empathy and communicative proficiency. Communication pleasure has demonstrated a good predictive relationship with empathy. It predictably has a beneficial impact on communication satisfaction. Nurse-patient contact is the foundation for nurses' empathy to be realized. The nurse might consider the circumstances and experiences of the patient when communicating. Role-taking is influenced by interpersonal communication styles and vice versa. The more two people are empathic with each other the more efficient their communication. It may be communicated, understood, and explored by identifying the emotion and by examining the patient's feelings and experience with the condition. By altering their behavior when providing bedside

patient care, nurses in the critical care unit can significantly reduce the negative impacts of communication impairment. Under ideal conditions, effective communication may be a demanding process. It takes more work to make sure the patient understands what is being said when they are in a troubled emotional state. Taking care of the patient's emotional needs enhances the patient's view of the dialogue. Because there is presently no standard for good nurse-patient communication, criticizing nurses' communication abilities may be impractical (Song et al., 2017).

To enhance nursing performance and the standard of critical care, training pertaining to communication skills should be incorporated into the phases of practical education. After establishing a nurse-patient relationship, the nurse ensures a positive patient experience. Patients can freely and honestly communicate their issues when there are therapeutic partnerships and good communication (Song et al., 2017).

Research conducted in 2021 by Choi et al. reveals a strong correlation between empathy and communication proficiency. Proficiency in communication refers to the capacity to convey knowledge effectively, either via spoken or written word. In order to enhance work performance as a nurse, a person must be able and ready to participate properly in transactions. This includes giving patients therapeutic environments and skillfully managing the demands of the hospital setting. Consequently, the therapeutic and administrative efficiency of a nurse relies on the collaboration with multidisciplinary team.

Challenges to empathy

There are several obstacles to empathy and strategies for overcoming them. The issues included failing to pay attention, experiencing the other person's emotions, failing to speak empathetically, and failing to share the other person's sentiments although knowing cognitively that empathy in communication is necessary. The

following strategies will help: 1) Reduce outside distractions while speaking with patients; 2) Develop nonverbal communication skills; 3) Gain a better understanding of voice tonality; and 4) Recognize that you can disagree with someone and yet be sensitive to their feelings (Swink, 2018).

Patients reported much higher empathy scores after a brief instruction, while observers reported significantly lower computer use by healthcare personnel. These results demonstrated that, in an academic medical facility, the quality of patient-centered care increased when patient-centered communication was incorporated into residency programs. This demonstrates why the training must be included into the residents' educational curriculum (Noordman, 2019).

Dikmen et al., (2016) state that critical care nurses are at risk of developing compassion fatigue. Empathy plays an important function in focusing burnout and managing job fulfillment, enhancing the job commitment (Yue et al., 2022)

A growing body of evidence suggests that burnout among ICU nurses can be caused by issues such as miscommunication (Curtis, 2014) and can lead to high levels of burnout (Song et al., 2017).

Strategies to improve communication competence and empathy

Communication competence and care behaviors have a positive correlation. In order to give nurses practical communication skills and to educate them about communication hurdles, new training tactics should be used. Nursing care must be administered by nurses using a scientific procedure called the nursing process. The best way to do this is through conversation, a social setting, and certain verbal and nonverbal communication techniques. Effective communication skills training given to nurses during their in-service has a beneficial influence rather than a negative one on

patient care (Kirca & Bademli, 2019). Nurses' in-service education might include scenario-based communication training. This can improve their communication performance in inpatient care and increase their competence and self-efficacy in communicating (Hsu et al., 2014).

According to Paternotte et al. (2015), in order to address patient requirements, novel and creative techniques are required. For example, health workers should be trained in intercultural communication skills that are relevant to interacting with patients from diverse cultural backgrounds. It is necessary to supplement educational programs in professional interpersonal communication (Song et al., 2017).

As such, nurses need to have excellent communication skills as a crucial part of cultivating empathy to care for patients as well as their families. The proposed role-play simulation program may be utilized to enhance communication abilities and increase communicative competence during nurse-to-doctor handover (Yu & Kang, 2017). Qualities such as cheerfulness, happiness, and a smiling demeanor created the impression that nurses were skilled (Wysong & Driver, 2009). Recognizing the patient's suffering and discomfort is crucial while delivering medical and surgical nursing care. This makes it easier to express sympathy and show that you genuinely care about the patient's well-being (Halpem, 2003).

Supporting evidence that nurses' actions can have a major influence on communication is provided by Song et al. (2017). In addition to augmentative and alternative communication tactics that may be used to guide patients and assist conversation, the findings highlight individual interaction behaviors that critical care nurses can implement into routine care interactions for patients on mechanical ventilation. In addition, the purposeful use of pleasant interactions by the nurses—like caressing and smiling—may inspire patients to converse and contribute to the

development of a therapeutic nurse-patient connection.

The online users indicated that social advocate enhanced successive feelings of pride, self-confidence, and prestige (Wohn & Lampe, 2018). The social support and empathy are “contagious”. The virtual consumers who received public assistance at their first post in the system as part of communication would be more likely to post again and provide approval for others. Furthermore, in-person communication trainings are useful for communicating the critical components of health professional communication as well as updates and decision-making to patients' families during pandemics. The COVID-19 epidemic necessitated a quick reexamination and may have a significant impact on how communication aspects are taught and learned (Hempel et al, 2021).

Demographic profile and Communication Competence

According to Onler et al. (2018), the communication skills score rose with age, employment experience, and years spent working in the same unit. However, it differs with Faraji et al, 2019 which implied that the communication skill score of nurses does not exhibit a statistically significant variation based on factors such as gender, age, educational background, or length of employment.

Patients' confidence and involvement in the treatment process rose as nurse-patient communication improved. The building of trust between healthcare professionals is impacted by factors including the gender, age, ethnicity, and health state of patients (Zare et al, 2020).

The educational background of the nurses, continuing education, and job satisfaction were the crucial factors influencing the integration of nurses' communication skills (Dithole et al, 2017).

After adjusting for sociodemographic factors, the only significant predictors of ICU nurses' success were their communication skills. Furthermore, Song et al. (2017) found that nurses with superior communication abilities tend to be older, possess a higher educational background, have more years of clinical and critical care unit experience, and earn a higher monthly pay.

In the study of Kounenou, Aikaterini, and Georgia (2011), it was also shown that only educational level and continuing education were the demographic characteristics that were strongly connected to communication. Work experience did not show any discernible correlation.

Demographic Profile and Empathy

The brain underpinnings of empathy vary according to age. Differences occur between adolescence and elderly age. Ages appear to have a big impact on how we portray and communicate the good and negative emotions of others, especially as we become older (Riya et al., 2018).

Age, gender, and experience are the factors associated with empathy. For example, older adults are thought to have more understanding than younger adults do (Williams et al., 2014). Additionally, research suggests that women tend to be more empathic than men (Berg et al., 2015), and that greater levels of understanding are often produced by both personal and professional patient experience (Chen, 2015).

A study also reported that empathy was negatively related to age. Female students showed superior empathy capacity in comparison to male students (Ferri et al., 2015). There is no evidence that older people have less ability to respond affectively to emotional displays, but there is less cognitive empathy for happiness and despair (Huhnel et al., 2014).

According to Schenk (2014), age and empathy have a substantial negative link; older nurses in her study scored worse on empathy than younger nurses. Remarkably, the study found no relationship between years of expertise and empathy.

Evidence suggests that the capacity for empathy varies in both the genders. Males are less emotional and more cerebral, whereas females are more caring and sympathetic. There is a suggestion that societal expectations around gender roles may be the primary cause of the observed gender inequalities. Despite these results, more statistical power should be used to investigate gender variations in empathy, and gender-specific characteristics should be taken into account (Moore et al., 2014). According to Abudari et al., (2016), the dominance of female nurses in the nursing field relative to that of male nurses. The public has a stereotype that associates nursing with femininity and non-masculinity since it is an innate trait related to caring for women (Buyuk et al., 2015). Because of this, the nursing profession has traditionally been associated with women, although more and more men are entering the field recently (Adeyemi-Adelanwa et al., 2016, LeBlanc et al., 2019).

Low educational status results in high harm avoidance in both genders. Greater levels of schooling were associated with higher levels of reward dependency in males and perseverance in women. There was no correlation between either gender's level of education and impulsive decision-making. Lower educational level was linked to temperament traits that were explosive and meticulous. Conversely, hand, reliable and passionate temperament profiles were seen in highly educated.

Cultural groups differed in how they expressed empathy nonverbally, which affected the standard of care and communication. Certain nonverbal cues seemed to be universally favored, whereas others seemed to be culturally particular (Lorie et al., 2017).

Work experience was shown to be the most significant demographic factor influencing empathy. Results also indicated that burnout and empathy were negatively correlated among cancer nurses (Taleghani, 2017). Another study indicated that there is an association between low empathy and high psychological distress. The cognitive reappraisal of approach coping acted as a mediator in this. It also results from avoidance dealing's desertion and shifting of blame. These findings provide a helpful model. This illustrates how the protective and enhancing roles of particular coping mechanisms influence how psychological distress is experienced in relation to empathetic capacity (Nodaa, 2018).

Culture and communication competence

As the nurses find a job to other countries, the individual encountered increased diversity in cultural, social, and linguistic settings. Getting in touch with patients at baseline is a difficult task. There are linguistic and cultural barriers between the patients, their families, and the physicians. Ethnicity, race, nationality, religion, regionalism, family, and affiliation with certain organizations, including professional or recreational ones, are all layers that make up culture. Due to differing cultural perspectives, the patient family and the team may interpret words and actions differently, which might lead to misunderstandings (Toole et al., 2019). As posited by Atkins, Uskul and Cooper (2016), culture shapes empathy since the way people infer and respond to the feelings and emotions of others vary depending on the cultural background.

The nurses' character such as having openness, understanding, respect, knowledge, and sensitivity regarding culture would be beneficial to patients. It will help in providing equal and ethical care, better adherence to treatments, effective interaction, and better recovery (Mosed et al, 2021).

According to the study of Schim et al 2006, that Higher education and cultural sensitivity and awareness are significantly correlated, and self-reported cultural competency practices and diversity training are correlated as well. The findings back up the call for further nursing education and training as well as increased funding for enhancing cultural competency. It is imperative that nurses treat each patient as an individual and consider their particular cultural demands. An interpreter or linguistic support is crucial when interacting with patients, relatives, and healthcare professionals from diverse cultural backgrounds. Moreover, the healthcare workers' resilience in adapting and learning the Arabic culture and language needs to be assessed. It is appropriate in providing optimal delivery of patient care (Hemberg & Vilander, 2017).

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on Hildegard Peplau's Interpersonal Theory. According to Peplau's (1952/1991) theory, how patients view health care is mostly influenced by the working phase of their interpersonal relationships with nurses. The idea that interactions between patients and nurses have the most impact on patients' evaluations of their experiences and level of satisfaction with care is widely acknowledged. In general, nurses help patients reach appropriate interpersonal anxiety levels. They support the patient's development, well-being, and health while facilitating strong pattern integrations on an interpersonal level.

Given that nursing entails interacting with several people towards a shared objective, it may be considered an interpersonal process. This objective serves as a catalyst for the healing process. Here, the interactions between the nurse and patient foster mutual respect and help them both learn and develop. Communication competency is one of the most important components of a nurse's work with patients,

as nurses spend the majority of their time communicating with patients and families in the intensive care unit (ICU). It also has a significant impact on how patients perceive their hospital stays (Ganey, 2013).

Furthermore, Peplau believed that nurses were vital to fostering therapeutic milieu. According to Kuhns (2007), nurses must treat patients with dignity, empathy, and acceptance as fellow human beings. Peplau's views are referred to as the interpersonal view of behavioral aberrations by Stuart and Sundeen (1987). This demonstrates how conduct changes in the setting of interpersonal relationships. This notion generally holds that more fulfilling activity arises from a positive relationship between the nurse and the patient. Closeness is shown to promote progress toward good conduct, empathy, trust, and self-esteem. Reeducating the patient on constructive ways to relate to the nurse is part of the therapeutic process.

The theory connects to a number of contemporary ideas, including client involvement, self-management by the client, motivational interviewing, and making educated decisions (D'Antonio et al., 2014). It lists the many functions that nurses play in patient care. Orientation, identification, exploitation, and resolution are its four stages. The nurse-client relationship's beginning is explained during the orientation phase. At this point, the client discloses the problem and requests the nurses' assistance. Identification involves nurses educating the client, and it builds respect towards meeting the client's needs. The exploitation phase focuses on client behavior modification and less dependent on the nurse. The client must be competent to handle themselves throughout the termination phase before the nurse may discharge them from their care (Adams, 2017). Subsequent research indicated that communicative skill, empathy, age, and clinical practice experience all had an impact on an individual's capacity for interpersonal relationships.

As applied to this study, this theory holds that communication competencies and empathy influence or explain the dependent variables such as age, gender, current work position, nationality, and length of ICU experience. This is because a reciprocal relationship and a shared perception of the situation are required, then interaction can be useful. Furthermore, the theory was also utilized to understand how nurses of different demographic profiles may have differences in their communication competence and empathy towards the patients.

Utilizing the theory provides a better and broader understanding of the effect of Communication Competency and Empathy among Nurses in their performance in the Intensive Care Unit of Tertiary Hospital, Saudi Arabia.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram Showing the Relationship of the Variables in the Study

The paradigm in figure 1 indicates the dependent variable which are the Level of Communication Competency in terms of public, meeting, group, dyad, stranger, acquaintance, friendship, and Empathy of Nurses in the Intensive Care Unit while the independent variables are the Nurses profile in terms of age, gender, educational attainment, current work, position, nationality, and length of ICU experience. These variables may or may not affect each other. Further, it also shows that the communication competence also served as the independent variable for empathy.

Operational Definition of Terms

The following are some of the terms used with their corresponding operational definitions in this study:

Communication Competence. This speaks to the ICU nurse's understanding of meaningful, acceptable, and productive engagement patterns as well as her capacity to apply and modify such understandings for each patient.

Communication. This is the process by which the patient and the ICU nurse engage in a continuous and dynamic sequence of high-quality interpersonal interaction that includes the exchange of verbal and nonverbal cues, which is directed towards the health status of the patient. In this study, specifically referred to the situations of which one might need to communicate such as communicating to friends, stranger, and acquaintances.

Empathy. This refers to awareness of the feeling and emotions of other people or the patients.

Intensive Care Unit. This refers to a department of Tertiary Hospital in Saudi Arabia in which patients who are dangerously ill are kept under regular observation of

their health conditions.

Meeting. This refers to communication to a large number of strangers, or a large number of friends, or a large number of acquaintances.

Public. This is speaking to a group of people that you are acquainted with, friends with, or strangers with.

Hypothesis of the Study

The following hypothesis will help this study to achieve its goals which is to identify the relationship between communication and empathy among ICU nurses in the Intensive Care Unit or none:

H_{a1}: There is significant relationship between the communication competence and empathy among ICU nurses of a tertiary hospital in Saudi Arabia.

H_{a2}: There is significant relationship between the communication competence and profile of nurses in the ICU in terms of age, gender, educational attainment, current work position, nationality, and length of ICU experience.

H_{a3}: There is significant relationship between the empathy and profile of nurses in the ICU in terms of age, gender, educational attainment, current work position, nationality, and length of ICU experience.

Chapter III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter covers the research instrument, research and experimental procedure, research methodology, research location, study respondents, sampling strategy, and statistical treatment. This chapter will give an overview and the complete methods of how the study was conducted.

Research Design

The study used a non-experimental quantitative design, which is used to describe, differentiate, or examine associations (Polit and Beck, 2014). In particular, descriptive correlation was employed.

A descriptive correlational study is utilized in this study since it is the most appropriate in answering the problems of this research. Studies using descriptive correlation analysis explain the variables and the organic connections that exist between and among them (Burns & Grove, 2005). A descriptive survey method was used to assess the socio-demographic profile of nurses which included the age, gender, current work position, level of educational attainment, nationality, and ICU work experience; self-perceive communication competency scale, and Toronto empathy questionnaire. Then these variables were also correlated; hence, the use of descriptive-correlational design.

Sampling Design

The researcher made use simple random sampling, which is the most basic probability sampling (Polit and Beck, 2014). In this method every individual in the population has a chance of being selected as a sample.

The respondents of this study came from Tertiary Hospital in Saudi Arabia that includes 243 nurses from 555 total ICU nurses: the Adult Cardiovascular Unit, Coronary Care Unit, General Intensive Care Unit, Pediatric Cardiovascular Unit, Neuro Intensive Care Unit, Pediatric Intensive Care Unit, Neonatal Intensive Care Unit 3, and Neonatal Intensive Care Unit 2.

A total of 243 nurses were needed to determine the relationship between competency and empathy. The sample size estimated for this cross-sectional study used following formula $=Z_{1-\alpha/2}^2 \frac{SD^2}{d^2}$, where $Z_{1-\alpha/2}$ is standard normal variate (5% type 1 error). SD standard deviation of variable, d = absolute precision and is taken as 0.05.

Excluded in the respondents are the ICU nurses with the length of experience below one year in the current work area.

Research Instrument

The research questionnaire utilized in the study consist of a demographic survey, Self -Perceived Communication Competence Scale (SPCC) and Toronto Empathy Questionnaire (TEQ).

McCroskey and McCroskey (1988) created the Self-perceived Communication Competence Scale (SPCC) to collect data on people's perceptions of their own competence as senders and recipients of various forms of communication. The respondent can define communication skill using this scale. People choose how and when to communicate (e.g., if they will even do it), their perception is important, outside observer. Moreover, this is a measure of perceived skill rather than real communication competency. Although there may be a strong correlation between these two distinct test kinds, they are not the same. It was designed to gauge one's own level of

perceived communication proficiency. Higher self-perceived communication competence with primary communication settings (public, meeting, group, and dyad) and recipients (strangers, acquaintances, and friends) is indicated by higher SPCC scores.

The Self -Perceived Communication Competence Scale (SPCC) tool presents twelve situations where the nurses might need to communicate. The ability of nurses to communicate effectively vary, and the competence to communicate differs from one situation to another. It will show how applicable they think they are to each of the circumstances listed below. The score ranging from:

No.	No. of Choices	Scoring
1.	Completely incompetent	0
2.	Competent	100

To compute the subscores, add the percentages for the items indicated and divide the total by the number indicated below

Public	1 + 8 + 12; divide by 3.
Meeting	3 + 6 + 10; divide by 3.
Group	4 + 9 + 11; divide by 3.
Dyad	2 + 5 + 7; divide by 3.
Stranger	1 + 4 + 7 + 10; divide by 4.
Acquaintance	2 + 6 + 9 + 12; divide by 4.
Friend	3 + 5 + 8 + 11; divide by 4.

To compute the total SPCC score, add the sub-scores for Stranger, Acquaintance and Friend. Then, divide that total by 3.

Reliability Mean .SD

Public	0.72	68.8	17.8
Meeting	0.68	68.8	17.1
Group	0.67	76.1	14.6
Dyad	0.44	81.1	12.4
Stranger	0.87	55.5	23.6
Acquaintance	0.84	77.4	15.3
Friend	0.78	88.2	11.3
Total	0.92	73.7	13.8

		< 51 Low
Public	> 86 High SPCC	SPCC
		< 51 Low
Meeting	> 85 High SPCC	SPCC
		< 61 Low
Group	> 90 High SPCC	SPCC
		< 68 Low
Dyad	> 93 High SPCC	SPCC
		< 31 Low
Stranger	> 79 High SPCC	SPCC
		< 62 Low
Acquaintance	> 92 High SPCC	SPCC
		< 76 Low
Friend	> 99 High SPCC	SPCC
		< 59 Low
Total	> 87 High SPCC	SPCC

Higher SPCC scores indicate higher self-perceived communication

competence with primary communication contexts (public, meeting, group, dyad) and receivers (strangers, acquaintance, friend).

The 16-item, five-point Likert scale, self-report, unidimensional Toronto Empathy Questionnaire was designed to gauge people's empathy levels. On a five-point rating system, from never to often, each item is evaluated. It views empathy as a transient phenomenon and a mostly emotional activity. The tool showed positive correlations with existing empathy and social decoding measures.

It measures the relation of empathic responding connected to emotional state of another person, comprehension, understanding physiological arousal and altruism. Items 1 and 4 particularly center on the observation of an emotional state in another that elicits the same emotion in the self. Item 8 measures how well people understand others' emotions. By indexing the frequency of behaviors exhibiting suitable sensitivity, it addresses the evaluation of emotional states in other people (items 2, 7, 10, 12, 15). The Toronto empathy questionnaire also contains items for sympathetic physiological arousal (items 3, 6, 9 and 11) and altruism (items 5, 14 and 16). Finally, one item inquires the frequency of behaviors engaging higher-order empathic responding, such as pro-social helping behaviors (item 13). Eight items are negatively scored (2, 4, 7, 10, 11, 12, 14, 15), reflecting the frequency of situational indifference towards another individual.

When combined, these questions show a broad range of behaviors associated to empathy that have been characterized. Scoring Item responses are scored according to the following scale for positively worded items 1, 3, 5, 6, 8, 9, 13, 16. Never = 0; Rarely = 1; Sometimes = 2; Often = 3; Always = 4. The following negatively worded items are reverse scored: 2, 4, 7, 10, 11, 12, 14, 15. Scores are summed to derive

total for the Toronto Empathy Questionnaire.

Legend:

- 0-0.8** **Very Low Level of Empathy**
- 0.81-1.6** **Low Level of Empathy**
- 1.61-2.4** **Moderate Level of Empathy**
- 2.41-3.2** **High Level of Empathy**

Validity

The extent to which an instrument measures what it is intended to measure is referred to as validity. It speaks about the research population and the tool's veracity. The consistency with which an instrument assesses a characteristic is known as reliability. A device that reduces the amount of mistake in a score obtained and records the correct scores. In establishing reliability, the following will be implemented (Polit and Beck, 2014).

The Self-Perceived Communication Competence Scale has a great face validity and has produced good alpha reliability estimates (above.85). Additionally, a significant amount of predictive validity has been discovered.

There are sixteen items in the Toronto Empathy Questionnaire, covering a broad variety of characteristics related to the theoretical aspects of empathy. It is believed that phenomena like emotional contagion are connected to the affective component of empathic responsiveness. Test-retest reliability, concept validity, and internal consistency of the questionnaire have all been demonstrated to be good (Spreng et al., 2009).

Data Gathering Procedure

To facilitate the gathering of data, the researcher has undertaken the following procedures:

1. *Seek permission.* the first step was the submission of the letter to the Institutional Review Board (IRB) at Tertiary Hospital in Kingdom of Saudi Arabia asking approval to conduct this study.

When granted, procedure approval was sought from the Medical Director of Critical Care Service Administration and Director of Nursing of KSHC and Critical Care Service Administration to obtain permission in administering the survey.

2. *Administration of the survey.* The respondents 243 ICU nurses were visited in their unit daily at the beginning of Day Shift thru Unit Manager and were given the sealed packet. ICU nurses were encouraged to answer on their convenient time. Approximately one week after the initial distribution of the survey, the researcher sent a reminder letter to all participants. At times, there is answered questionnaire during daily visits, it will be collected and entered to the database. The questionnaires were tallied and tabulated based on the statistical analysis plan.

The cover letter, inside address, research purpose, survey instructions, informed consent, and questionnaire were all enclosed in the sealed envelope. There was also a clarification given on confidentiality in the handling of the survey data. Anonymity was guaranteed, and participants were instructed not to provide their names on the completed survey. The privacy of the gathered data was preserved. The purpose of this was to make it more likely that nurses would feel comfortable sharing their impressions on the empathy and communication in their units.

3. *Retrieval of the questionnaire.* The answered survey questionnaires were collected from the respondents. Those who have not given the survey questionnaires were followed-up after a week. The researcher thanked the respondents by giving them a token of appreciation.

Figure 2. Data Gathering Procedure

Ethical Considerations

The investigator ensured that relevant research protocols were adhered to and specific Communication Competency and Empathy Among Nurses...

ethical considerations were taken into account during the study's execution.

Social Value. This study paved the way for better understanding about the communicative competence and empathy of Intensive Care Unit nurses. From the result of the study, nurses may be given technical assistance on how they can improve their communication competence and empathy towards their patients; hence, this would result to better patient care.

Informed Consent. The researcher ensured that all respondents have voluntary consent to be part of this study. Informed consent clearly indicates the purpose of the research and that their participation is voluntary. They were also given the option to withdraw anytime during the progress of the study, without incurring any consequences. The respondents were also given the time and opportunities to clarify and ask questions about the study and they may also decline whenever they have doubts during their participation in the process of research.

Privacy and confidentiality of information. The researcher made sure that the personal information of the respondents was handled with utmost confidentiality. The transcribed data were used for this purpose of research, and it was ensured that no identity was connected to any individual's answers. Based on the Data Privacy Act of 2012, anonymity was also strictly adhered.

Justice. The researcher always considers fairness. In dealing with the respondents, their rights were protected, and they were given the fair treatment in the conduct of the study.

Permission to organization. A letter of permission was sent to the Hospital Administrator to allow the proponent to conduct the study. Once the permission was obtained, then the researcher started to gather the data from the nurses.

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Presented in this section are the results of the analyzed data with their corresponding discussions. The issue statement that was presented at the start of the research provides the basis for how the presentation is organized.

Table 1

Demographic Profiles

Demographic Profiles	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age		
20-29	24	10
30-39	58	23.5
40-49	155	64
50-59	5	2
60 and above	1	0.5
Gender		
Male	13	5
Female	230	95
Nationality		
Indian		
Filipinos	120	49
Others (Saudi, Jordanian, Pakistani, South African)	99	41
	24	10
Educational Attainment		
Diploma	88	36
BSN	150	62
Master's degree	5	2
Current Work Position		
Staff Nurse 1	168	69
Staff Nurse 2	64	26
Shift Manager	10	4.5
Unit Manager	1	0.5
Length of Service		
1-10 years	103	43
10-20years	140	57

Table 1 shows the demographic profiles of the respondents. Most of the respondents are between ages 40 to 49 years old comprising 155 (64%). There are 58 respondents who are in the age range of 30 to 39 years old or 23.5%. Out of 243 respondents, there are 24 respondents who belong to the age bracket of 20 to 29

years old which in turn comprise 10%. One (1) of the respondents belong to the age bracket of 60 years old and above or 0.5 %. The data implies that most of the respondents are middle adulthood while the least is 60 years old and above.

Regarding the frequency and percentage distributions of respondents according to gender, the data show that majority or 95% of respondents are female and 5% of the respondents are male. It implies that majority of the respondents are female as compared to males. According to Abudari, Ibrahim and Aly (2016), the dominance of female nurses over their male counterparts in the nursing field. The public has a stereotype that associates nursing with femininity and non-masculinity as an innate trait related to caring for women Buyuk, Korkmaz, and Rizalar (2015). As a result, until recently, the nursing profession was seen as exclusively the domain of women, albeit men are gradually entering the field (Adeyemi-Adelanwa et al., 2016, LeBlanc et al., 2019).

The frequency and percentage distributions of respondents according to nationality shows that majority of the respondents are Indian with 49%; followed by ninety-nine (99) respondents who are Filipinos with 41%. Other nationality which composed of Saudi, Jordanian, Pakistani, and South African comprising 24 respondents (10%) of the sample.

For distribution of respondents according to educational attainment, the data show that 62 % or 150 of the respondents are having Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) degree. This is followed by 88 respondents or 36% who are having Diploma level and five (5) respondents or 2% are master's degree holder.

The data imply that majority of the respondents are Staff Nurse 1 with 69 %; followed by Staff Nurse 2 with 26%. There are 10 respondents who are Shift Managers with 4.5% comprising the sample and 0.5% for Unit Manager.

Self- Perceived Communication competence among nurses in the ICU

Table 2

Self- Perceived Communication competence among nurses in the ICU

Primary Communication Contexts	Standard Deviation	Mean
Public	31.79	88.62
1. Present a talk to a group of strangers.	41.93	77.37
8.Present a talk to a group of friends.	9.05	99.18
12.Present a talk to a group of acquaintances.	30.98	89.3
Meeting	38.87	81.48
3.Talk to a large meeting of friends.	18.92	96.3
6.Talk in a large meeting of acquaintances.	36.78	83.95
10.Talk in a large meeting of strangers.	48.04	64.2
Group	22.52	94.65
4.Talk in a small group of strangers.	32.96	87.65
9.Talk to a small group of friends.	9.05	99.18
11.Talk to a small group of friends.	16.76	97.12
Dyad	31.28	89.03
2.Talk with an acquaintance.	30.98	89.3
5.Talk to a friend.	11.07	98.77
7.Talk to a stranger.	40.81	79.01
Stranger	39.99	77.06
1. Present a talk to a group of strangers.	41.93	77.37
4.Talk in a small group of strangers.	32.96	87.65
7.Talk to a stranger.	40.81	79.01
10.Talk in a large meeting of strangers.	48.04	64.2
Acquaintance	29.43	90.81
2.Talk with an acquaintance.	30.98	89.3
6.Talk in a large meeting of acquaintances.	36.78	83.95
9.Talk to a small group of friends.	9.05	99.18
12.Present a talk to a group of acquaintances.	30.98	89.3
Friendship	26.54	97.84
3.Talk to a large meeting of friends.	18.92	96.3
5.Talk to a friend.	11.07	98.77
8.Present a talk to a group of friends.	9.05	99.18
11.Talk to a small group of friends.	16.76	97.12
Overall	19.44	88.44

Table 2 shows the self-perceived communication competence among nurses in the ICU. The data presented the perceived communication competence of nurses in communicating during the situations of which one might need to communicate such as communicating to friends, stranger, and acquaintances in a variety of contexts.

As shown in the data, the ICU nurses have high perceived communication competence when communicating in public and in group with the mean of 88.62 (standard deviation 31.79) and 94.65 (standard deviation 22.52) respectively. As reflected in the scoring guide for SPCC, in public context, when the mean is greater than 86, this means the perceived communication competence is High; while in group, the mean greater than 90 is also considered High perceived communication competence.

The mean of the participant replies (88.62, standard deviation 31.79) indicates that the participants feel more at ease when they are in a large group with other communication partners. This suggests that speakers in larger groups may feel more anonymous. Anxiety and panic are lessened by this sense of anonymity. Because he or she believes that not many people in the group know them, the speaker takes the chance of speaking in front of a large gathering and maybe making blunders. When nurses have higher communication competence, their adaptability in their environment can be improved; quality of nursing is enhanced; relationship among nurses and patients can be promoted Curtis et al., (2013). It can help in decision making process during clinical rounds and affects the communication collaboration between patients and nurses.

Meanwhile, in other contexts such as meeting (mean of 81.48, standard deviation 38.87) and dyad (mean 89.03, standard deviation 31.28) with the same receivers to strangers, friends, and acquaintances; the nurses' self-perceived communication

competence is Moderate. This implies that nurses in the ICU can communicate with moderate level of competence with the patients who are strangers to them, who are considered their friends and or acquaintances regardless of whether the context is public, meeting, group, or dyad. In the ICU, patients come from different walks of life and indeed, they meet new people, friends, and acquaintances whom they need to communicate as part of patient care.

According to the article of Yoo, Lim and Shim (2020), ICU nurses found it more difficult to communicate with patients, their families, and caregivers than it was to carry out basic nursing tasks (such as giving medications, suctioning, and using different mechanical devices). Their communication problems were either system-related or nurse-to-patient and family. Different issues in an ICU are tied to urgency; patients who are experiencing a cardiac arrest, respiratory failure, or hemodynamic instability, for instance, may be given priority.

Overall, the Self- Perceived Communication competence among nurses in the ICU result showed mean of 88.44 (standard deviation 19.44).

Empathy among nurses in the ICU

Table 3

Level of Empathy Among Nurses in the ICU

Statements	Standard Deviation	Mean
1. When someone else is feeling excited, I tend to get excited too	1.01	2.31
2. Other people's misfortunes do not disturb me a great deal	1	2.26
3. It upsets me to see someone being treated disrespectfully	1.06	2.96

4. I remain unaffected when someone close to me is happy	1.3	2.89
5. I enjoy making other people feel better	0.8	3.51
6. I have tender, concerned feelings for people less fortunate than me	0.99	2.94
7. When a friend starts to talk about his\her problems, I try to steer the conversation towards something else	1.29	2.73
8. I can tell when others are sad even when they do not say anything	1.01	2.51
9. I find that I am "in tune" with other people's moods	1	2.3
10. I do not feel sympathy for people who cause their own serious illnesses	1.29	2.86
11. I become irritated when someone cries	1.16	3.16
12. I am not really interested in how other people feel	1.05	2.26
13. I get a strong urge to help when I see someone who is upset	0.96	2.94
14. When I see someone being treated unfairly, I do not feel very much pity for them	1.26	2.51
15. I find it silly for people to cry out of happiness	1.18	2.94
16. When I see someone being taken advantage of, I feel kind of protective towards him\her	1.11	2.56
Overall	0.44	2.72

Presented in table 3 is the level of empathy among nurses in the ICU. The instrument consists of 16-item statements to measure level of empathy. It specifies the aspect of empathy as measured in the study and the mean scores generated.

Two items on the Toronto Empathy Questionnaire (TEQ)—item 1 with a mean score of 2.31 and item 4 with a mean score of 2.89—focus particularly on the observation of an emotional state in another that elicits the same emotion in oneself. The results show that sometimes, the nurses are affected by the emotions of others. In some instances, they are excited or happy when others are excited or happy. In a state of excitement people think and behave very differently (Patel et al., 2017) which can also be contagious to others.

One item assesses emotion comprehension in others (item 8). The respondents of this study have moderate level of empathy as shown in the mean of 2.31. The result shows that sometimes, nurses can tell when others are sad even without telling them.

Items 2, 7, 10, 12, and 15 illustrate adequate sensitivity and measure the emotional states of others by indexing the frequency of behaviors. Items 7, 10, 12, and 15 also reveal high levels of empathy exhibited by nurses. In item 2, the nurses scored Moderate level of empathy with the mean of 2.26 of which sometimes, for the nurses, the other people's misfortune do not disturb them in great deal. Nurses always show empathy by starting to talk with people who have problems; but they always do not feel sympathy for people who cause their own serious illnesses. According to the study of Shensheng (2019), there is a multifaceted nature of concerns for social justice, self-evaluation, and social identity.

Some of the questionnaire's items discuss sympathetic physiological arousal (items 3 with mean 2.96, item 6 with mean 2.94, and 11 with mean 3.16), showing

moderate level of empathy. For the respondents of the study, they are sometimes upset to see someone being treated disrespectfully; they have tender, concerned feelings for people less fortunate than them; and they become irritated when someone cries.

In terms of altruism as depicted in item 5 with mean of 3.51; item 14 with the mean of 2.51; and item 16 with the mean of 2.56, nurses show both moderate and high level of empathy. They have high level of empathy as they always enjoy making other people feel better. They also exhibit a moderate level of empathy, as they occasionally feel that when they witness someone being mistreated, they do not feel very sorry for them, and occasionally they feel somewhat protective of the person being exploited.

The respondents of this study have day and night duties rhythm. According to the study of Chung et al, 2009; Compared to ordinary morning shift nurses, permanent night shift nurses have increased sympathetic activity when they sleep. Over time, working night shifts may have an impact on nurses' sleep patterns. As per the study of Ono et. al (2012), in all scenarios, sympathetic nerve tone rose. Subjective tension and higher physiological activity were seen when someone expressed empathy for another person's unpleasant feeling. Empathy-related physiological reactions rely on an understanding of several subjective elements. While the right temporal area of the brain was stimulated while discussing negative feelings, bilateral frontal activity was decreased when comprehending negative emotions was thought about.

Additionally, one item looks at how frequently people engage in higher-order empathic responses, such as pro-social helping activities, which are shown in item 13 with a mean score of 2.94, which indicates that people feel compelled to assist

when they witness someone in distress. This indicates a high degree of empathy.

Three items were also moderately scored (1, 2, 9), reflecting the frequency of situational indifference towards others. When someone else is excited, they occasionally have a tendency to get enthusiastic too, and other people's tragedies do not bother them too much. They also exhibit a modest degree of empathy, as evidenced by their perception of being "in tune" with other people's emotions.

According to the study of Light et al (2019), while in the company of someone who is experiencing bad emotions, one might show good emotions in order to help the other feel less negative by encouraging the other person to feel positive emotions (for example, by trying to "cheer" the person). Similar to this, someone might express happiness to make someone else happy even if they are only feeling neutral or pleased already. We might refer to this kind of positive-valence empathy as empathetic cheerfulness. Moreover, a person may feel happy vicariously in reaction to another person's good feeling (e.g., enjoy improving the lives of others), a phenomenon known as empathetic happiness.

Relationship between the communication competence and empathy among nurses in the ICU of a tertiary hospital in Saudi Arabia

Table 4.

Significant Relationship between the Level of Self Perceived Communication Competence and Level of Empathy of the Respondents

Variables	Spearman's Rho	P-value
Level of Empathy	0.030	0.639

The level of self-perceived communication competence and level of empathy of the nurses in the ICU was tested through Spearman's Rho. It shows the p-value of

0.639 which is considered as not significant since the relationship value yield a negligible result. This means, though the generated mean for the level of communication competence is high, this has no effect or has no correlation to level of empathy the nurses have.

The result is in contrary of the findings of Redmond (1985) who found out that there is a significant relationship between communication competence and empathy. While Song et al. (2017) offers data to support the claim that nurses' actions may have a major influence on patients' communication, highlighting certain interaction behaviors that should be demonstrated to patients, this current study finds the otherwise. As shown in the result, both variables do not exhibit significant relationship.

In the current study, demographic profile of the respondents composed of 96% expatriates and providing nursing care to Muslim patients in a predominantly Muslim nation reveals that foreign-born nurses see themselves as helpless patient advocates hampered by the nurse-patient-family-physician quadriad structure and the influence of cultural norms on expectations for particular nonverbal expressions in patient-clinician dyads. (Lorie et al.,2017). Expatriate nurses face several challenges with their work (due to their religion, culture, and language), nurse to patient communication barriers and workplace incivility (Alosaimi & Ahmad, 2016). Most expatriate nurses were not satisfied with their quality of work life (Alreshidi, & Alsharari, 2021). As nurses loaded by different human relationships with healthcare professionals, patients, and caregivers during clinical practice and this in turn causes stress, which has a negative effect on successfully forming significant relationships (Han, 2010).

According to Levett-Jones et al. (2019), a systematic review that examined the efficacy of empathy training for undergraduate nursing students found evidence that training in empathy and communication skills enhances nursing students' empathy,

and that nursing communication education plays a predictive role in students' empathic skills (Ozturk & Kacan, 2022).

Relationship between the communication competence and profile of nurses in the ICU

Table 5.

Significant Relationship between the Communication Competency and Profile of nurses in the ICU in terms of Demographic Profile

Variables	P Chi-Square	df	Significance
Age	27.645 ^a	21	.151
Gender	3.179 ^a	2	0.20
Educational Attainment	35.529 ^a	14	.001
Current Work position	3.074 ^a	6	0.80
Nationality	9.245 ^a	12	0.68
Length of ICU Experience	25.306 ^a	21	.234

Table 5 exhibits the relationship of communication competence and profile of nurses in terms of age, gender, educational attainment, current work position, nationality and length of ICU experience. As shown in the data, educational attainment generated a significant relationship with the communication competence with the chi square 35.529^a (significance 0.001) which is lower than .05 level of significance, while the age, gender, current work position, nationality and length of ICU experience do not show significant relationship.

Based on the result, communication competence has significant relationship with educational attainment which means, the perceived communication competence is higher among nurses with higher educational attainment. The higher level of education

they obtained, the higher is their perceived communication competence. However, age, gender, current work position, nationality and length of ICU experience relationship do not exhibit the same significance.

It can be gleaned from the result that for nurses to have higher communication competence, they also need to strive for advanced education. This result supports the idea that the educational background of the nurse's, continuing education is the crucial factors influencing the integration of nurses' communication skills. However, it contradicts with Onler et al. (2018) who emphasized that communication skills score increased with age, job experience, and working years in the same unit.

The result implies that whether the nurses are male or female; regardless of the work position they have in the ICU; and whether they are Filipinos or belong to other nationality, there is no evidence in this study that these have link to the level of communication competence.

Indeed, as the nurses find a job to other countries, the individual encountered increased diversity in cultural, social, and linguistic settings. Getting in touch with patients at baseline is a difficult task. There are linguistic and cultural barriers between the patients, their families, and the physicians. Ethnicity, race, nationality, religion, regionalism, family, and affiliation with certain organizations, including professional or recreational ones, are all layers that make up culture. Due to differing cultural perspectives, the patient family and the team may interpret words and actions differently, which might lead to misunderstandings (Toole et al., 2019).

The nurses' character such as having openness, understanding, respect, knowledge, and sensitivity regarding culture would be beneficial to patients. It will help in providing equal and ethical care, better adherence to treatments, effective

interaction, and better recovery (Mosed et al, 2021).

Relationship between the empathy and profile of nurses in the ICU

Table 6.

Significant Relationship between the Empathy and Profile of nurses in the ICU in terms of demographic profile

Variables	P Chi-Square	df	Significance
Age	157.122 ^a	102	0.00
Gender	0.507 ^a	3	0.92
Educational Attainment	73.537 ^a	68	0.302
Current Work position	18.919 ^a	18	0.10
Nationality	5.769 ^a	9	0.03
Length of ICU Experience	147.820 ^a	102	0.002

Table 6 shows the data on the relationship between empathy and profile of nurses in the ICU. As presented, age (significance 0.00), nationality (significance 0.03), length of ICU experience (significance 0.002) exhibited significant result while gender, educational attainment and current work position are not significant.

The results imply that there is a significant correlation between age, nationality, length of ICU experience and empathy while gender, educational attainment and current work position in the ICU, there is none. The results imply further that the increase in the level of empathy is observed among older nurses. The increase of level of empathy is evident in the increase of age.

This significant relationship of age and level of empathy is also observed in other research. The degree of empathy varies throughout age groups, particularly from adolescence to old age, since the presentation and sharing of good and negative

emotions by individuals at different ages, particularly those in their later years, is greatly influenced by these factors. This study supports Williams et al. (2014) who found out that older adults are thought to have more understanding than younger adults. This, however, contradicts Schenk's (2014) findings, which show that older nurses in her study scored worse on empathy than their younger colleagues, demonstrating a substantial negative link between age and empathy.

The nationality of the nurses in the ICU has significant relationship with the level of empathy as evidenced with significance of 0.03 which is lower than the 0.05 level of significance. This means, level of empathy is correlated to the nationality of the nurses. Indeed, different nationality manifest different cultural beliefs which interweave with the way people express and share their emotions towards others like in the cases of nurses with their patients. As posited by Atkins et al., (2016), culture shapes empathy since the way people infer and respond to the feelings and emotions of others vary depending on the cultural background.

The length of ICU experience (significance 0.002) has significant relationship with empathy. According to Moghaddasian's (2013) article, the majority of ICU nurses exhibited a high degree of empathy for hospitalized patients. Additionally, the study found that work experience was the most significant demographic factor influencing nurses' empathy, but there was no correlation between nurses' gender, education level, or marital status. These findings are consistent with Gleichgerrcht and Decety's (2013) findings that nurses with more work experience had higher empathy scores, but there was no correlation between nurses' age, gender, educational attainment, or marital status..

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

This chapter provides an overview of the study's findings, which focused on identifying the important correlation between nurses' levels of empathy and self-perceived communication ability in the intensive care unit of a tertiary hospital in Saudi Arabia. Additionally, it determined how various characteristics—such as age, gender, educational background, duration of ICU experience, gender, current job position, and nationality—related to the profile of the responders.

The study was conducted at Tertiary Hospital in Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The respondents were 243 Intensive Care Unit nurses in Saudi Arabia. They were selected using simple random sampling. It employed descriptive correlation as design of the study, adapted questionnaire instruments were used. These were the Self -Perceived Communication Competence Scale (SPCC) by McCroskey and McCroskey (1988) and Toronto Empathy Questionnaire (TEQ) by Prof. Nathan Spreng. The statistical tools used were mean, frequency distribution, percentage, standard deviation, Spearman Rho and Chi-square.

The ICU nurses have High perceived communication competence when communicating in public and in group with the mean of 88.62 (standard deviation 31.79) and 94.65 (standard deviation 22.52) respectively. Meanwhile, in other contexts such as meeting the data revealed mean of 81.48 (standard deviation 38.87), dyad with mean of 89.03 (standard deviation 31.28), friendship with mean of 97.84 (standard deviation 26.54) and acquaintances result with mean of 90.81(standard deviation

29.43) . Overall, the strangers, meeting, dyad, friendship, and acquaintances result is Moderate.

Furthermore, the level of empathy among ICU nurses is High with the overall mean of 2.72 and standard deviation of 0.44.

The level of self-perceived communication competence and level of empathy of the nurses in the ICU was tested through Spearman's Rho. It shows the p-value of 0.639 which is considered as not significant since the relationship value yield a negligible result. This means, though the generated mean for the level of communication competence is High, this has no effect or has no correlation to level of empathy the nurses have.

The educational attainment generated a significant relationship with the communication competence with the chi square 35.529^a (significance 0.001) which is lower than .05 level of significance, while the age, gender, current work position, nationality and length of ICU experience do not show significant relationship.

The data on the relationship between empathy and profile of nurses in the Intensive Care Unit presented age with (significance 0.00), nationality (significance 0.03), length of ICU experience (significance 0.002) exhibited significant result while gender, educational attainment and current work position are not significant.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the presented data, the ensuing conclusions were made:

1. There is no discernible correlation between the nurses' strong empathy and their assessed high degree of communication ability in the Saudi Arabian hospital's intensive care unit.

2. Intensive Care Unit nurses perceived communication competence is significantly linked to their educational attainment of which the more advanced their education, the higher is their level of communication competence.

3. The findings revealed that Intensive Care Unit nurses level of empathy is correlated to age, nationality and length of experience of the nurses in the ICU.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of the study generate the following recommendations:

1. The higher level of perceived communication competence among nurses in the ICU is evident that they are believed they can talk with patients in public, in group contexts and moderate level in some respects. This level of communication competence may be strengthened and improved by offering them more trainings on how to communicate with patients in different contexts.

2. The level of empathy among nurses was found out High. The hospital may check on this and may find way techniques on how to strengthen the empathic behavior among their nurses. Since the level of empathy is High and Moderate in other areas, the hospital administration may look into this matter for sustainability, provide more educational training and recognizing their accomplishments for nurses to have very High level of empathy.

3. The hospital administration may check on the features of communication competence and empathy among ICU nurses as it addresses shared governance to improve nursing practice in the organization.

4. The future researchers may conduct the same research with the use of another set of measures or instruments to find out if the same results could be generated.

5. Future research about the following related to this topic may be considered since these will provide further explanation regarding the empathy of nurses coming from different nationalities considering that culture is also varied. Also, another study on the factors affecting empathy may also be conducted to understand how empathy can be affected by different situations or contexts.

a. Qualitative study focusing on the empathy of nurses who come from different nationality.

b. Quantitative study about the factors affecting empathy of nurses in the ICU.

REFERENCES

- Abudari, M., Ibrahim, F., & Anwar, A. (2016). "Men in nursing" as viewed by male students in secondary schools." *Clinical Nursing Studies* 4(2), 41.
- Adams, A., Mannix, T., & Harrington, A. (2017). Nurses Communication with families in the Intensiv Care Unit- A Literature review. *Nurs.Crit.Care*.
- Adams, L. (2017). Peplau's Contribution to Nursing Knowledge. *J Mental Health Addic. Nurs.*, 1(1), e10-e18.
- Adeyemi-Adelanwa, O., Barton-Gooden, A., Dawkins, P., & Lindo, J. L. (2016). Attitudes of patients towards being cared for by male nurses in a Jamaican hospital. *Applied Nursing Research*, 29, 140-143.
- Arora, V., Eastment, M., & Bethea, E. (2013). Participation and experience of Third-Year medical students in handoffs: time to sign out? *J. Gen Int Med*, 28, 994-998.
- Alosaimi, D. N., & Ahmad, M. M. (2016). *The challenges of cultural competency among expatriate nurses working in Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Research and Theory for Nursing Practice*, 30(4), 302–319. <https://doi.org/10.1891/1541-6577.30.4.302>.
- Almutairi, K. (2015). Culture and language differences as a barrier to the provision of quality care by the health workforce in Saudi Arabia. *Saudi Med J.*, 36 (4).
- Alreshidi, N. M., & Alsharari, A. F. (2021). Work-life balance of expatriate nurses working in acute care settings. *Nursing Open*, 8, 320.
- Alsulaimani, A.(2014). Practical competency of Filipino Nurses working in Taif City, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. *Saudi Journal for Health Sciences*, 3(2).
- Atkins, D., Uskul, A. K., & Cooper, N. R. (2016). Culture shapes empathic responses to physical and social pain. *Emotion*, 16(5), 587.
- Bach, S., & Grant, A. (2009). *Communication and Interpersonal Skills for Nurses*. Learning Matters Ltd. 61-67. Available at: www.learningmatters.co.uk.
- Bartlett, G., Blais, R., Tamblyn, R., Clermont, R.J., & MacGibbon, B. (2008). Impact of patient communication problems on the risk of preventable adverse events in acute care settings. (*CMAJ*) *Canadian Medical Association Journal*.
- Beauregard, M. (2009). Effect of mind on brain activity: evidence from neuroimaging studies of Psychotherapy and placebo effect. *Nord. J. Psychiatry*, 63(1), 5-16.
- Bentur, N. (2019). The implementation of a structured communication tool improves family satisfaction and expectations in the intensive care unit. *Journal of Critical Care*, 51, 6-1.
- Berg, K., Blatt, B. J., Lopreiato, J.J., Jung, A., Schaeffer, A., Heil, D., & Hojat, M. (2015). Standardized patient assessment of medical student empathy:

Ethnicity and gender effects in a multi-institutional study. *Academic Medicine*, 90(1), 105-111.

- Boyle, D.K., Miller, P.A., & Forbes-Thompson, S.A. (2005). Communication and end-of-life care in the Intensive care unit: patient, family, and clinician outcomes. *Crit.Care Nurs Q.*, 28(4), 302-316.
- Bridges, J., et al. (2013). Capacity for Care: Meta-Ethnography of Acute Care Nurses' Experiences of the Nurse-Patient Relationship. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 69(4), 760–72.
- Buyuk, E. T., Rizalar, S., Korkmaz, M. (2015). *Male nurses: the perspectives of the hospitalized children's mothers. International Journal of Caring Sciences*, 8(3), 729.
- Carroll, SM. (2007). Silent, slow lifeworld: the communication experience of nonvocal ventilated Patients. *Qualitative Health Research*, 17(9), 1165–1177.
- Chen, Y., Xu, Y. (2021). Exploring the Effect of Social Support and Empathy on User Engagement in Online Mental Health Communities. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 18(13), 6855.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18136855>
- ChuChen, Y., Chen, C., Decety, J., & Cheng, Y. (2014). *Aging is associated with changes in the neural Circuits underlying empathy. Neurobiology of Aging* 35(4), 827-836.
- Chung, M.H., Kuo, T.B., Hsu, N., Chu, H., Chou, K.R., & Yang, CC. (2009). Sleep and autonomic nervous system changes - enhanced cardiac sympathetic modulations during sleep in permanent night shift nurses. *Scand J Work Environ Health*, 35(3), 180-7. <https://doi: 10.5271/sjweh.1324>
- Curtis, J.R, Sprung, CL., & Azoulay, E. (2014). The importance of word choice in the care of critically ill patients and their families. *Int. Care Med.*, 40, 606-608.
- Curtis, J.R., Back, A.L., Ford, D.W., Downey, L., Shannon, S.E., & Doorenbos, A.Z. (2013). Effect of communication skills training for residents and nurse practitioners on quality of communication with patients with serious illness: a randomized trial. *JAMA*, 310 (21), 2271-2281.
- Christov-Moore, L., Simpson, E. A., Coude, G., Grigaityte, K., Iacoboni, M., & Ferrari, P.F. (2014). Empathy: Gender effects in brain and behavior. *Neuroscience and bio-behavioral reviews*, 46(4), 604–606.
<https://doi:10.1016/j.neubiorev.2014.09.001>.
- D'Antonio, P., Beeber, L., Sills, G., & Naegle, M. (2014). *The future in the past: Hildegard Peplau and Interpersonal relations in Nursing.*
- Dal Santo, L., Pohl, S., Saiani, L., & Battistelli, A. (2014). Empathy in the emotional interactions with patients. Is it positive for nurses too? *Journal of Nursing Education and Practice*, 4(2).

- Deligianni, A., Kyriakidou, M., Kaba, E., Kelesi, M., Rovithis, M., Fasoi, G., & Stavropoulou, A. (2017). Empathy Equals Match: The Meaning of Empathy as It Is Perceived by Greek Nurse Students-A Qualitative Study. *Global Journal of Health Science*, 9(1), 171-171.
- Dikmen, Y., Aydin, Y., & Tabakoglu, P. (2016). Compassion fatigue: A study of critical care nurse in Turkey. *Journal of Human Sciences*, 13(2).
- Dithole, K.S., Thupayagale-Tshweneagae, G., & Akpor, O.A. (2017). Communication skills intervention: promoting effective communication between nurses and mechanically ventilated patients. *BMC Nurs.*, 74
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-017-0268-5>
- Duarte, J., Gouveia, J.P., & Cruz, B. (2016). Relationships between nurses' empathy, self-compassion and the dimension of professional quality of life: A cross-sectional study.
- Drews, F. A. (2013). Human factors in critical care medical environments. *Reviews of Human Factors and Ergonomics*. 8, 103–148.
<https://DOI:10.1177/1557234X13493250>.
- Embriaco, N., Papazian, L., Kentish-Barnes, N., Pochard, F., & Azoulay, E. (2007). Burnout Syndrome among critical care healthcare workers. *Curr Opin Crit Care*, 13(5), 482-488.
- Fallowfield, L., & Jenkins, V. (2004). *Communicating sad, bad and difficult news in Medicine*. *Lancet* 363:312-9.
- Ferri, P., Guerra, E., Marcheselli, L., Cunico, L., & Di Lorenzo, R. (2015). *Empathy and burnout: an analytic cross-sectional study among nurses and nursing students*. *Acta Biomed*, 86(2), 104-115.
- Ficarra, B. (2018). *How empathy can help to empower patients*.
<https://www.huffingtonpost.com/entry/why-empathy-empowers-pati783138.html>.
- Gleichgerricht, E., & Decety J. (2013). Empathy in clinical practice: How individual dispositions, gender, and experience moderate empathic concern, burnout, and emotional distress in physicians. *PloS One*, 8, e61526.
- Galajda, D. (2012). *Perceived Competence and Communication Apprehension – the Affective Variables of Willingness to Communicate in L1 and FL*.
- Gelinas, C. Fillion, L., Robitaille, MA., & Truchon, M. (2012). Stressors experienced by nurses Providing end-of-life palliative care in the intensive care unit. *Can J Nurs Res.*, 44(1), 18-39.
- Gerchow, L., Burka, L. Miner, S., & Squires, A. (2021). Language barriers between nurses and patients: A scoping review. *Patient Education and Counselling*, 104(3).
- Giger, J., & Davidhizar, R. (2002). The Giger and Davidhizar Transcultural Assessment Model. *Journal of Transcultural Nursing*, 13(3). Sagepub.

Guerrero, J.G. (2019). Nurses towards End-of-life Situations: Sympathy vs Empathy. *Open Journal of Nursing*, 9, 278-293.

Gruber, M., & Hartman, R. (2007). Don't overlook "communication competence." *Nursing Management*, 38(3), 12-14.

Halligan, P. (2006). Caring for patients of Islamic denomination: Critical care nurses' experiences in Saudi Arabia. *J Clin Nurs.*, 15, 1565-1573.

Hamilton, J., & Woodward-Kron, R. (2010). Developing cultural awareness and intercultural communication through multimedia: A case study from medicine and the health sciences. *Fuel and Energy Abstracts*, 38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2010.09.015>.

Han, J. (2010). Nursing students' perceptions of clinical learning environment (CLE). *Journal of the Korean Data Analysis Society*, 12(5), 2595-607

Happ, M.B., Garrett, K., & Thomas, D.D. (2011). Nurse –patient communication interactions in the Intensive care unit. *American Journal of Critical care*, 20, 46-60.

Happ, M.B., Garrett, K., DiVirgilio, D., Thomas, J., Tate, E.G., Houze, M., Radtke, J. Kourkouta, L., Papathanassiou, I.V. (2014). Communication in Nursing Practice, *Sociomed*, 26(1), 65–7.

Hemberg, J.A.V., & Vilander, S. (2017). Cultural and communicative competence in the caring relationship with patients from another culture. *Scand J Caring Sci.*, 822-829. <https://doi.org/10.1111/scs.12403>.

Hempel, L., Kiessling, C., Löffler-Stastka, H., Philipp, S., Rockenbauch, K., Schnabel, K.P., & Zimmermann, A. (2021). Special issue on teaching social and communicative competences - status quo. *GMS J Med Educ*.

Hendrich, A., Chow, M. P., Skierczynski, B. A., & Lu, Z. (2008). A 36-hospital time and motion Study: how do medical-surgical nurses spend their time? *The Permanente Journal*, 12(3), 25–34.

Hong, S., & Bae, S.-Y. (2019). *Convergence Factors Related with Communication Competency of Students in Health Majors in Studying for TOEIC*. *Journal of Digital Convergence*, 17(5), 257–266. <https://doi.org/10.14400/JDC.2019.17.5.257>.

Hsu, L.L., Huang, Y.H., & Hsieh, S. (2014). The effects of scenario-based communication training on nurses' communication competence and self-efficacy and myocardial infarction knowledge. *Patient Education and Counseling*, 95(3), 356-364.

Huhnel, I., Folster, M., Werheid, K., & Humboldt, U.H. (2014). Empathic reactions of younger and older adults: No age-related decline in affective responding. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 50, 136-143. Berlin, Germany.

Hu, Y.Y., Arriaga A., Roth, E.M., Peyre, S.E, Swanson, R.S., & Osteen, R.T. (2011). Protecting Patients from an unsafe system. *J Am Coll Surg*, 213(3).

- Ijssennagger, C.E., Ten, C.E., Hoorn, S., Van Wijk, A., Van den Broek, J.M., Girbes, A.R., & Tuinman, P.R. (2018). Caregivers' perception towards communication with mechanically ventilated patients: The results of a multicenter survey. *J Crit Care*, 48, 263- 268.
- Järvinen, K. (2015). Adulthood temperament and educational attainment: A Population-Based cohort study. *Learning and Instruction*, 40, 39-53.
- Kahriman, I., Nural, N., Arslan, U., Topbas, M., Can, G., & Kasim, S. (2016). The Effect of Empathy Training on the Empathic Skills of Nurses. *Iranian Red Crescent Medical Journal*, 18(6), e24847. <https://DOI:10.5812/ircmj.24847>.
- Karlsson, V., Bergbom, I., & Forsberg, A. (2012). The lived experience of adult intensive care patients being conscious during mechanical ventilation: A phenomenological hermeneutic approach. *Intensive and Critical care Nursing*, 28, 6-15.
- Kataoka, H., Iwase, T., Ogawa, H., Mahmood, S., Sato, M., DeSantis, J., Hojat, M., & Gonnella, J. (2018). Can communication skills training improve empathy? A six-year longitudinal study of medical students in Japan, *Medical Teacher*, <https://DOI: 10.1080/0142159X.2018.1460657>.
- Kirca, N., Bademli, K. (2019). Relationship between communication skills and care behaviors of nurses. *Perspectives in Psychiatric Care*. 10.1111/12381.
- Koukkouta, L., & Papathanasious, I. (2014). Communication in Nursing Practice. *Materia Sociomedica*, 26(1)65-7.
- Lane-Fall, M.B., Pascual, J.L., & Peifer, H. G. (2018). A partially structured postoperative handoff Protocol improves communication in 2 mixed surgical intensive care units: findings from the Handoffs and Transitions in Critical Care (HATRICC). A prospective cohort study. *Ann Surg.*, 271(3), 484-493. <https://doi: 10.1097/SLA.0000000000003137>.
- Lee, Young Bu, & Koh, Myung Suk. (2015). The effect of communication ability and emotional intelligence of clinical nurses on organizational performance. *Journal of Korean Clinical Nursing Research*, 21 (3), 347–354.
- Levett-Jones., Cant, R., & Lapkin, S. (2019). A systematic review of the effectiveness of empathy education for undergraduate nursing students. *Nurse education Today*, 75, 80-94.
- Light, S.N., Moran, Z.D., Zahn-Waxler, C., & Davidson, R. (2019). The Measurement of Positive Valence Forms of Empathy and Their Relation to Anhedonia and Other Depressive Symptomatology, *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10.
- Lorie, A., Rienero, D., Philips, M., Zhang, L., & Riess, H. (2017). Culture and nonverbal expressions of empathy in clinical settings: A systematic review. *Patient Educ Couns.*, 100(3), 411-424. <https://doi: 10.1016/j.pec.2016.09.018>.
- Mahoney, D. (2013). Nurse communication: a rising tide measure. *Partners*, 4-5.

- Mercer, S., & Reynolds, W. (2002). Empathy and quality of care. *Brit J Gen Pract.*, 52, S9- S13. Pubmed.
- Merckaert, I., Delevallez, F., Gibon, A.S., Lienard, A. Y., Libert, A., N., & Delvaux, N. (2015). Transfer of communication skills to the workplace: impact of a 38-hour communication skills training program designed for radiotherapy teams. *J Clin Oncol*, 33 (8), 901-909.
- Merritt, M.K., & Procter, N. (2010). Conceptualizing the functional role of mental health consultation-liaison nurse in multi-morbidity, using Peplau's nursing theory. *Contemp Nurse*, 34 (2), 158-166.
- Mahmoudi, M., Moghaddasian, S., & Lakdizaji, S. (2013). *Nurses Empathy and Family Needs in the Intensive Care Units. J Caring Sci.*, 2(3): 197–201. <https://doi:10.5681/jcs.2013.024>
- Mitchell, M.L., Coyer, F., Kean, S., Stone, R., Murfield, J., & Dwan, T. (2016). Patient, family-centred care interventions within the adult ICU setting: an integrative review. *Aust Crit Care.*, 29, 179–193. pmid:27592540
- Mosed, H., Periord, M., Caboral-Stevens, M. (2021). A concept analysis of intercultural communication. *Nurs Forum.* 2021 Oct;56(4):993-999. doi: 10.1111/nuf.12622.
- Murillo, A., Colomer, S., Peco, H. (2017). *Communication skills in ICU and adult hospitalization Unit nursing staff.* *Inferm Intensiva.*
- Naji, G., Isha, A., Alazzani, A., Saleem, M. S., Alzoraiki, M. (2022). *Assessing the Mediating Role of Safety Communication Between Safety Culture and Employees Safety Performance.* *Frontiers in public health*, 10, 840281. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.840281>
- Neelam, W. (2018). *Strength of Speaking and Communication for Students.* Jakarta: Karya Mandiri, 22 - 25.
- Noordman, J., Post, B., van Dartel, A., Slits, J., & Olde Hartman, T. C. (2019). Training residents in patient-centred communication and empathy: evaluation from patients, observers and residents. *BMC medical education*, 19(1), 128. <https://doi:10.1186/s12909-019-1555-5>.
- Ouzouni, C., & Nakakis, K. (2012). An exploratory study of student nurse's empathy. *Health Sci J.*, 6(3), 534-552.
- Onler, E., Yildiz, T., & Bahar, S. (2018). Evaluation of the communication skills of the operating room staff. *Journal of Interprofessional Education & Practice*, 10, 44-46.
- Ozturk, A., Kacan, H. (2022). Compassionate communication levels of Nursing students: Predictive role of empathic skills and nursing communication course. *Perspect Psychiatr Care*, 58, 248-255.

- Park, Y. S., & Oh, E. G. (2018). Factors Related to Intensive Care Unit Nurses' Patient Centered Communication Competency. *Journal of Korean Critical Care Nursing*, 11(2), 51-62.
- Patel, S., Wallis-Redworth, M., Jackson, S., & Rose, L. (2017). Art and science: Promoting understanding and empathy through film. *British Journal of Midwifery*, 25(11), 734-740.
- Paternotte, E., Van Dulmen, S., Van der Lee, N., Scherpbier, A. J., & Scheele, F. (2015). Factors Influencing intercultural doctor-patient communication: A realist review. *Patient Educ Couns.*, 98, 420-445.
- Piquette, D., Reeves, S., & Leblanc, V. R. (2009). Interprofessional intensive care unit team Interactions and medical crises: A qualitative study. *J Interprof Care*, 23(3), 273-285.
- Piazza, O., & Cersosimo, G. (2015). Communication as a basic skill in critical care. *J Anaesthesiol Clin Pharmacol*, 31(3), 382-383.
- Polit, D., & Beck, C. T. (2014). *Essentials of Nursing Research. Appraising Evidence for Nursing Practice*. 4th Edition. Wolters Kluwer, Lippincott William, and Wilkins.
- Pollmann, M., & Krahmer, E. J. (2018). How Do Friends and Strangers Play the Game Taboo? A Study of Accuracy, Efficiency, Motivation, and the Use of Shared Knowledge. *Journal of language and social psychology*, 37(4), 497-517. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0261927X17736084/>
- Puntillo, K. A., Smith, D., Arai, S., & Stotts, N. (2008). Critical care nurses provide their Perspectives of patients' symptoms in intensive care units. *Heart Lung*, 37(6), 466-475.
- Kristanto, R., & Kurniawati, W. (2020). *Public Speaking Serta Teknik Ice Breaking. Jurnal Komunitas: Jurnal Pengabdian kepada Masyarakat*, 2(2), 127 - 132.
- Lee, S. H., Phan, P. H., Dorman, T., Weaver, S. J., & Pronovost, P. J. (2016). Handoffs, safety culture, and evidence from the hospital survey on patient culture. *BMC Health Servs Res.* 16, 254. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-016-1502-7>
- Rabol, L., Andersen, M., & Ostergaard, D. (2011). Descriptions of verbal communication error between staff. An analysis of 84 root cause analysis-reports from Danish hospitals. *BMJ. Qual Saf.*, 20, 268-74.
- Randal, S. C., & Wayne, S. (2013). *Elements of effective communication*. 4th edition. Washington: Plain & Precious Publishing.
- Redmond, M. V. (1985). The relationship between perceived communication competence and perceived empathy. *Communications Monographs*, 52(4), 377-382.

- Riya, F., Tschernegg, M., Chiesa, P., Wagner, I., K., Kronbichler, M. Lamm, C., & Silami, G. (2018). Age-Related differences in the neural correlates of empathy for pleasant and unpleasant touch in a female sample. *Neurobiology of Aging*, 65, 7-17.
- Riordan M. A., & Trichtinger L. A. (2017). Overconfidence at the keyboard: Confidence and accuracy in interpreting affect in email exchanges. *Human Communication Research*, 43, 1-24.
- Rothschild, J.M, Landrigan, C.P, Cronin, J.W, Kaushal, R., Lockley, S.W, & Burdick, E. (2005). The Critical Care Safety Study: the incidence and nature of adverse events and serious medical errors in Intensive Care. *Crit Care Med.*, 33(8):1694e700.
- Rodak, A.C., Slusarska, B., Nowicki, G., Ogorek, M., Zarzycka, D., Niedorys, B., & Dziedzic, E. (2019). Selected socio-demographic and work-related determinants of the social competence of professionally active nurses. *Nursing in the 21st Century*, 18(2), 12-20. <https://doi.org/10.2478/pielxxiw-2019-0006>
- Rhoads, S., & Amass, T. (2019). Communication at the End-of-Life in the Intensive Care Unit: A Review of Evidence-Based Best Practices. *Rhode Island Medical Journal*, 2;102(10), 30-33. PMID: 31795531.
- Rushton, P., & Ankey, D. (1996). Brain size and cognitive ability: Correlations with age, sex, social class, and race. *Psychon. Bull. Rev.*, 3(1), 21-36.
- Serafin Danilewicz, D., Chyla, P., & Pączek, B. (2020). What is the most needed competence for newly graduated generation z nurses? Focus groups study. *Nurse Education Today*, 94.
- Schenk, J.J. (2012). *The Emotional Intelligence Profile of Successful Nurses*. The Journal of Continuing Education, 43(8), 354-362. <https://doi:10.3928/00220124-20120615-44>
- Sinclair, S., Beamer, K., Hack, T., McClement, S., Raffin, S., Chochinov, H., & Hagen, N. (2017). Sympathy, empathy, and compassion: A grounded theory study of palliative care patients' understandings, experiences, and preferences. *Palliative Medicine*, 31(5).
- Son, Y.J., Lee, Y. A., Sim, K. N., Kong, S. S., & Park, Y.S. (2013). Influence of Communication Competence and Burnout on Nursing Performance of Intensive Care Units Nurses. *Journal of Korean Academy of Fundamentals of Nursing. Korean Association of Fundamentals*, 20(3), 278. <https://doi.org/10.7739/jkafn.2013.20.3.278>.
- Shahbaz, M., Khan, R., Khan, M., & Mustafa, G. (2016). Role of Self-Perceived Communication Competence and Communication Apprehension for Willingness to Communicate in L1 and L2. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 6(1). <https://DOI:10.5901/jesr.2016.v6n1p158>

Shensheng, W., Scott, L., & Philippe, R. (2019). Schadenfreude constructed and reconstructed: A tripartite motivational model. *New Ideas in Psychology*, 52.

Skills and Activities for Effective Group Communication. (2017).
<https://study.com/academy/lesson/skills-activities-for-effective-group-communication.html>.

Song, H.S., Choi, J., & Son, Y.J. (2017). The relationship between professional communication Competencies and nursing performance of critical care nurses in South Korea. *Int J. Nur Pract.*, 23(5). <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijn.12576>

Son, Y.J., Lee, Y. A., Sim, K. N., Kong, S. S., Park, Y.-S. (2013). Influence of Communication Competence and Burnout on Nursing Performance of Intensive Care Units Nurses. *Journal of Korean Academy of Fundamentals of Nursing*, 20(3), 278–288. <https://doi.org/10.7739/jkafn.2013.20.3.278>.

Spreng, R.N., McKinnon, M.C., M., & Levine, B. (2009). The Toronto Empathy Questionnaire: Scale Development and Initial Validation of a Factor-Analytic Solution to Multiple. *J Pers Assess*, 91(1), 62-71.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00223890802484381>.

Stanley S., & Sethuramalingam, V. (2015). Empathy in social work: implications for practice. *IJPR*, 20, 51–61.

Schim, S.M., Doorenbos, A., Borse, Z., & Nagesh N. (2006) Cultural Competence Among Hospice Nurses. *Journal of Hospice & Palliative Nursing*, 8(5), 302-307.

Swink, D. (2018). I Don't Feel Your Pain: Overcoming Roadblocks to Empathy. *Psychology Today*. <https://www.psychologytoday.com/intl/blog/threat-management/201303/i-dont-feel-your-pain-overcoming-roadblocks-to-empathy>

Taleghani, F., Ashouri, E., & Saburi, M. (2017). Empathy, Burnout, Demographic Variables and Their Relationships in Oncology Nurses. *Iranian journal of nursing and midwifery research*, 22(1), 41–45. <https://DOI:10.4103/ijnmr>

Toghian, C.N., Ahrari, S., & Alikhah, S. (2014). Comparison of the effect of teaching of SBAR technique with role play and lecturing on the communication skill of nurses. *J Caring Sci*, 3 (2), 141-147.

Toole, J.M., Alvarado, W., Christy, J.W. (2019). Communication with Diverse Patients: Addressing Culture and Language. *Pediatric Clinics of North America*, 66(4), 791-804. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pcl.2019.03.006>.

Tomomi, Y., Nodaa, T., Takahashib, Y., & Toshiya, M. (2018). Coping mediates the association. between empathy and psychological distress among Japanese workers. *Personality and Individual Difference*, 124, 178-183.

Usta, Y.Y., Demir, Y., & Yarmoruglo, H. (2012). Nurses perspective on positive attitude to cancer Patients in Turkey: A qualitative study. *Asian Pacific Cancer Prevention*, 1225-1229.

- Wanga, Y.Y., Qiao-Qin, W., Linb, F., Zhoua, W.J., & Shang, S.M. (2017). Interventions to improve Communication between nurses and physicians in the intensive care unit: An integrative literature review. *International Journal of Nursing Sciences*, 5(1), 81-88.
- Weller, M. Boyd, D., & Cumin, T. (2014). Teams, tribes, and patient safety: overcoming barriers to Effective teamwork in healthcare. *Postgrad Med J*, 90 (1061), 149-154.
- Westwick, J.N., Hunter, K.M., & Haleta, L.L. (2016). A Digital Divide? Assessing Self-Perceived Communication Competency in an Online and Face-to-Face Basic Public Speaking Course. *Basic Communication Course Annual*, 28(11).
- Wheelan, SA., Burchill, CN., Tilin F. (2003). *The link between teamwork and patients' outcomes in intensive care units. American Journal of Critical Care: An Official Publication, American Association of Critical-Care Nurses;12(6):527.*
[PubMed]
- Williams, B., Brown, T. SBAR, Boyle, M, McKenna, L., Palermo, C., & Etherington, J. (2014). Levels of empathy in undergraduate emergency health, nursing, and midwifery students: A Longitudinal study. *Advances in Medical Education and Practice*, 5, 299-306.
- Yeh, VJ., Sherwood, G., Durham, C., Edgren, S.K., Schwartz, T., & Beeber, L. (2019). Designing and implementing asynchronous online deliberate practice to develop interprofession communication competency. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 35, 21-26.
- Yu, M., & Kang, K.J. (2017). Effectiveness of a role-play simulation program involving the technique: A quasi-experimental study. *Nurse Education Today*, 53, 41-47.
- Yu, S., & Ko, Y. (2017). Communication competence as a mediator in the self-leadership to job performance relationship. *Collegian*, 24(5), 421-425.
- Yue, Z., Qin, Y., & Li, Y. (2022). Empathy and burnout in medical staff: mediating role of job satisfaction and job commitment. *BMC Public Health*, 22, 1033.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-022-13405-4>
- Zeighami, R., Rafiei, F., & Parvizi, S. (2012). Concept analysis of empathy in nursing. *J Qual Res Health Sci.*, 1(1), 27–33.
- Zhu, B., Chen, Z., Liang, X., Liang, B. (2016). Mediating effect of self-efficacy in the relationship between emotional intelligence and clinical communication competency of nurses. *International Journal of Nursing Sciences*, 3(2), 162-168.

Appendices

APPENDIX A

Questionnaire/Tool for Data Collection

RESEARCH TOOL

Questionnaires/Tool for Data Collection

Before we begin, please be assured that all the information you provide in this survey is entirely anonymous. When answering the questions, please tick (✓) the number that best represents your answer. Although answering every question is preferable, you have the right to skip any item that you do not want to answer. Please read all the instructions carefully and answer each question as accurately as possible.

Part 1. Demographic Data

1.Age	20-29	40-49	
	30-39	50-59	
2.Gender	Male	Female	
3.Nationality	Saudi	Non-Saudi	
4.Education level	Diploma	Master	Other (Specify)_____
	Bachelor	PhD	
5.Current work Position	SN1	Shift manager	
	SN2	Unit Manager	
6. How many years have you practiced as a critical care nurse?	2-5 years	10-15 years	
	6-10 years	More than 20 years	

Self- Perceived Communication Competence Skills (SPCC)

Directions: Below are twelve situations in which you might need to communicate. People's abilities to communicate effectively vary a lot, and sometimes the same person is more competent to communicate in one situation than in another. Please indicate how skilled you believe you are to deliver in each of the conditions described below. Indicate in the space provided at the left of each item your estimates of your competence.

Presume 0=complete incompetent and 100 =competent.

- _____ 1. Present a talk to a group of strangers.
- _____ 2. Talk with an acquaintance.
- _____ 3. Talk to a large meeting of friends.
- _____ 4. Talk in a small group of strangers.
- _____ 5. Talk to a friend.
- _____ 6. Talk in a large meeting of acquaintances.
- _____ 7. Talk to a stranger.
- _____ 8. Present a talk to a group of friends.
- _____ 9. Talk to a small group of friends.
- _____ 10. Talk in a large meeting of strangers.
- _____ 11. Talk to a small group of friends.
- _____ 12. Present a talk to a group of acquaintances.

Toronto Empathy Questionnaire

Please read each statement carefully and rate how frequently you feel or act in the manner described. Circle your answer on the response form. There are no right or wrong answers or trick questions. Please answer each question as honestly as you can.

		Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
1.	When someone else is feeling excited, I tend to get excited too	0	1	2	3	4
2.	Other people's misfortunes do not disturb me a great deal	0	1	2	3	4
3.	It upsets me to see someone being treated disrespectfully	0	1	2	3	4
4.	I remain unaffected when someone close to me is happy	0	1	2	3	4
5.	I enjoy making other people feel better	0	1	2	3	4
6.	I have tender, concerned feelings for people less fortunate than me	0	1	2	3	4
7.	When a friend starts to talk about his\her problems, I try to steer the conversation towards something else	0	1	2	3	4
8.	I can tell when others are sad even when they do not say anything	0	1	2	3	4
9.	I find that I am "in tune" with other people's moods	0	1	2	3	4
10.	I do not feel sympathy for people who cause their own serious illnesses	0	1	2	3	4
11.	I become irritated when someone cries	0	1	2	3	4
12.	I am not really interested in how other people feel	0	1	2	3	4
13.	I get a strong urge to help when I see someone who is upset	0	1	2	3	4
14.	When I see someone being treated unfairly, I do not feel very much pity for them	0	1	2	3	4
15.	I find it silly for people to cry out of happiness	0	1	2	3	4
16.	When I see someone being taken advantage of, I feel kind of protective towards him\her	0	1	2	3	4

Appendix B IRB Approval

Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
Ministry of Health
King Fahad Medical City
(162)

المملكة العربية السعودية
وزارة الصحة
مدينة الملك فهد الطبية
(١٦٢)

IRB Registration Number with KACST, KSA: H-01-R-012
IRB Registration Number with OHRP/NIH, USA: IRB00010471
Approval Number Federal Wide Assurance NIH, USA: FWA00018774

December 11, 2019

IRB Log Number: 19-578

Department: Nursing Department - KSHC

Category of Approval: EXEMPT

Dear Rhodora Mae Solis,

I am pleased to inform you that your submission dated November 13, 2019 for the study titled '**Communication Competency and Empathy among Nurses in the Intensive Care Unit of Tertiary Hospital in Saudi Arabia**' was reviewed and was approved according to Good Clinical Practice guidelines. Please note that this approval is from the research ethics perspective only. You will still need to get permission from the head of department or unit in KFMC or an external institution to commence data collection.

We wish you well as you proceed with the study and request you to keep the IRB informed of the progress on a regular basis, using the IRB log number shown above.

Please be advised that regulations require that you submit a progress report on your research every 6 months. You are also required to submit any manuscript resulting from this research for approval by IRB before submission to journals for publication.

As a researcher you are required to have current and valid certification on protection human research subjects that can be obtained by taking a short online course at the US NIH site or the Saudi NCBE site followed by a multiple choice test. Please submit your current and valid certificate for our records. Failure to submit this certificate shall a reason for suspension of your research project.

If you have any further questions feel free to contact me.

Sincerely yours,

Prof. Omar H. Kasule

Chairman, Institutional Review Board (IRB)

King Fahad Medical City, Riyadh, KSA

Tel: + 966 1 288 9999 Ext. 26913

E-mail: okasule@kfmc.med.sa

Appendix C

Approval to Use Toronto Empathy Questionnaire

Mon, May 27, 4:49 PM (3 days ago)

Nathan Spreng, Prof.

to me

Thank you for your interest. You are welcome to use and reproduce the Toronto Empathy Questionnaire for non-commercial research and educational purposes without seeking my written permission. The distribution must be controlled, meaning only to the participants engaged in the study or enrolled in the educational activity. Any other type of reproduction or distribution of the TEQ is not authorized without my written permission. The original Journal of Personality Assessment paper should be referenced in any resulting publication or report.

Best,
Nathan Spreng

R. Nathan Spreng, PhD
Associate Professor
Laboratory of Brain and Cognition
Montreal Neurological Institute
Department of Neurology and Neurosurgery
McGill University
e: nathan.spreng@gmail.com; nathan.spreng@mcgill.ca

Appendix D

N300 Gantt Chart

		Assigned Date	Achieved	Changed													
TASK		2019	Marc	April	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec					
1	Identify a topic for research																
2	Discussion with the Professor																
3	Submit a draft proposal																
4	Discussion with the Professor																
5	First draft																
6	Second draft																
7	Third draft																
8	Application for IRB approval																
9	IRB approval																
10	Medical Director/DON permission																
11	Start Data collection																

Assigned Date
Achieved
Changed

TASK	2020	Jan	Feb	Mar	April	May	Jun	July	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan 2021
1	IRB approval													
2	Medical Director/DON permission													
3	Start Data collection													
4	Questionnaire Distribution													
5	Complete Data collection													
6	Do further literature review													
7	Data analysis and preparing presentation and findings													
8	Writing up													
9	First Draft													
10	Second Draft													

Appendix E

Approval to use SPCC

Fri, May 31, 11:40 PM (4 days ago)

Lynda McCroskey <Lynda.McCroskey@csulb.edu>

to LMCCROSK@calpoly.edu, me

Dear Rhodora Mae Solis:

I am happy to grant you permission to use the SPCC and related measures/scales for your research project. I wish you great success!

Best regards--

Dr. Linda L. McCroskey

Associate Professor of Communication Studies
California State University, Long Beach. USA
805.550.9654 (text messaging okay)
562.985.4111 (Campus operator)
A/S 347 - office